

Swiss Farmers' Views on Cover Crop Practice and Climate Change

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Abstract

This thesis investigates Swiss farmers' views on cover crop practices and climate change using a mixed-methods approach, integrating Q-Methodology and qualitative interviews. Cover crops offer multiple potential benefits for increasing the sustainability of agricultural systems, particularly in the context of climate change. Furthermore, Swiss legislation on subsidies is already mandating their implementation. However, understanding how these practices are applied in real-world farming and identifying the incentives for farmers to adopt cover crops are critical for informing policy and promoting sustainable agriculture. This study provides insights into farmers' goals, motivations, and challenges regarding cover crop use and climate change adaptation.

Three distinct farmer viewpoints emerged from the analysis: *regenerative farmers*, who prioritize soil health; *economic farmers*, who emphasize cost-efficiency, immediate effects on subsequent crops and often use cover crops primarily for forage; and *sustainable-conventional farmers*, who balance forage production with environmental considerations. The research also highlights differing preferences for cover crop types among these groups. *Regenerative farmers* favor green manure crops to enhance soil health, while *economic farmers* tend to prioritize fodder crops for livestock feed.

Farmers exhibited diverse views on climate change, generally acknowledging more negative than positive impacts, such as increased weather extremes. No one expressed climate change denial. However, most were not overly concerned about the immediate effects on their own farms. Despite the challenges, many farmers demonstrated optimism and a proactive attitude, with cover crops playing an essential role as an adaptation measure to climate change. Other key adaptation strategies identified include the introduction of drought-resistant crop varieties and the implementation of advanced technologies.

Additionally, the study uncovered further emerging challenges for Swiss agriculture during the interviews, emphasizing the need to integrate these concerns into the broader discourse on agricultural sustainability.

Overall, this research provides a valuable foundation for understanding the complex decision-making processes of Swiss farmers regarding the use of cover crops and their adaptation to climate change. These findings can serve as a basis for more targeted policy decisions and communication strategies, ultimately promoting more sustainable agricultural practices.

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1 Introduction

Cover crops are planted between two main crops with the primary objective of maintaining soil cover ([Kaspar & Singer, 2011](#)). Typically sown in early autumn, these intermediate crops provide soil coverage throughout the winter. Their management varies; some are winter killed, while others are mowed or terminated through tillage in spring ([Bench & Hilshey, 2024](#)). Generally, cover crops are intended to benefit the soil and the agricultural system rather than being cultivated for commercial purposes ([Clark, 2007](#)). The various cover crops existing, serve different objectives depending on their plant composition. These crops offer numerous positive ecosystem services ([Wolters, 2020](#); [Lu et al., 2007](#); [Koudahe et al., 2022](#)), including mitigation and adaptation to climate change ([Yoder et al., 2021](#)). Efforts such as the use of cover crops are becoming increasingly important, given the critical stage of climate change ([Koudahe et al., 2022](#)).

The agriculture sector is one of the primary drivers of climate change ([Balogh, 2020](#); [EPA, 2018](#)). It significantly contributes to climate change through direct emissions from agricultural activities such as livestock farming, fertilizer use, and cultivation in greenhouses. Additionally, deforestation and the degradation of peatlands play significant roles in the release of greenhouse gases ([Ellens et al., 2017](#)). Not only is the food sector a major emitter of CO_{2e} emissions, but it is also significantly affected by the adverse impacts of climate change ([Mbow et al., 2022](#)). Reduced soil water availability, extreme weather events such as hailstorms, and the spread of currently temperature-limited agricultural diseases will affect agriculture in mid-latitude regions ([IPCC, 2022](#)). Moreover, climate change exacerbates soil erosion, posing a significant threat to soil fertility in the 21st century. Therefore, climate change will have major consequences for agriculture and jeopardize food security ([Mbow et al., 2022](#)).

Carbon compounds in soil play a crucial role in climate change mitigation by enhancing the absorption of atmospheric carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide ([European Commission, 2011](#)). Cover crops significantly contribute to the sequestration of these greenhouse gases ([Adetunji et al., 2020](#); [Ruis & Blanco-Canqui, 2017](#)). Moreover, cover crops are instrumental in climate change adaptation. They enhance soil water retention ([Adetunji et al., 2020](#)), protect against erosion during heavy rainfall ([Wolters, 2020](#)), and stabilize soil temperature while improving soil structure ([Daryanto et al., 2018](#)). These benefits increase soil resilience, which is essential in the context of a warming climate where mitigating water loss and soil heating using cover crops becomes increasingly important.

Beyond climate benefits, cover crops provide numerous other ecosystem services and positive agricultural effects ([Koudahe et al., 2022](#)). They enhance soil fertility through humus accumulation, potentially leading to long-term yield increases ([Finney & Kaye, 2016](#)). Cover crops can retain nutrients, prevent leaching and ensure nutrient availability for subsequent crops. This nutrient retention also reduces groundwater contamination by preventing soil particle runoff ([Clark, 2007](#)). Cover crops provide habitats for organisms, thereby promoting biodiversity and sustaining beneficial organisms ([Murrell et al., 2017](#)). Additionally, they compete with weeds, reducing their ability to establish ([Finney & Kaye, 2016](#)). Some cover crops, depending on the species, can be harvested for livestock feed or sold, such as hemp fibers ([Caton, 2019](#)).

However, there are potential drawbacks to using cover crops. While they can reduce pest pressure on main crops, under certain circumstances, they might also sustain pests that could negatively impact subsequent crops ([Adetunji et al., 2020](#)). Additionally, there are other disadvantages, such as increased labor requirements and potentially high seed costs ([Snapp et al., 2005](#)). Integrating cover crops into crop rotations can be challenging, as crop rotation compatibility must be ensured ([Finney & Kaye, 2016](#)). The timing of cover crop planting must align with the overall system, sometimes necessitating late-seeding mixtures suitable for specific conditions ([Liebig et al., 2015](#)). To maximize benefits and minimize drawbacks, farmers must carefully consider species selection and sowing time to avoid competition with main crops and reduce nutrient immobilization risks ([Wayman et al., 2014](#)). The advantages and disadvantages of cover crops depend largely on the species chosen and the specific goals farmers aim to achieve. Therefore, it is essential not only to examine cover crops themselves but also to understand the practical considerations that farmers make when deciding to incorporate them. This broader perspective is important in Swiss agriculture to address diverse agricultural and environmental goals, which requires a holistic approach.

Farmers play a central role as decision-makers in agricultural systems. To understand the behavior of farmers in sustainable agriculture and climate change, a targeted agricultural system approach is essential. Farmers' decisions are not only embedded in the biophysical setting, but their social identity also plays a crucial role ([Frank et al., 2011](#)). Understanding farmers' decision-making processes is essential for enhancing and promoting sustainable farming practices ([Feola et al., 2015](#)). Gaining deeper insight into cover crop practices specifically requires examining farmers' viewpoints on this issue, as their goals, motivations, and challenges are key to effective implementation.

Several studies have explored the adoption of cover crops and their relationship with farming practices. One significant barrier to cover crop adoption is the range of challenges farmers must overcome to successfully implement them ([Roesch-McNally et al., 2017](#)). Agronomic concerns, such as the disruption of planting and harvesting schedules, as well as difficulties in terminating cover crops, are more pronounced among large-scale farms and present a significant obstacle for them ([Carlisle, 2016](#)). Additionally, non-adopters often cite the time and labor required for planting and managing cover crops as another significant hurdle ([Myers & Wilson, 2023](#)). Despite these hurdles, some farmers who had adopted cover crops were ultimately surprised by the positive effects on cash crop yields. These outcomes had not only agricultural but also political implications in the USA ([Myers & Watts, 2015](#)). This finding suggests that many farmers are not fully aware of the potential benefits of cover crops and tend to focus more on the perceived obstacles ([Myers & Watts, 2015](#)). In addition to the focus on barriers, research has also examined the relationship between farming systems and cover crop practices to identify potential patterns. One key factor related to decisions on cover crops is the type of farming system. For example, studies have shown that organic farmers are more likely to invest in cover crop seeds and place a higher value on the ecosystem services provided by cover crops compared to conventional farmers ([Wayman et al., 2016](#)). Similarly, another study found a correlation between no-tillage practices, reduced fertilizer use, and the increased adoption of cover crops, suggesting that less intensive farming systems tend to rely more on cover crops ([Lira & Tyner, 2018](#)).

Overall, research highlights both the challenges and opportunities associated with cover crop adoption, emphasizing the importance of understanding farmers' viewpoints and the farming systems they operate in.

Several studies have explored various aspects of farmers' decision-making processes regarding cover crop practices ([Roesch-McNally et al., 2017](#); [Burnett et al., 2018](#); [Church et al., 2020](#); [Golden et al., 2023](#)). However, most of the existing studies primarily focus on the barriers and incentives for cover crop adoption, particularly in the context of the USA. What remains largely unexplored are the specific goals and motivations of farmers who already use cover crops, especially in other regions like Switzerland.

This research gap forms the foundation of my master thesis, which explores the goals Swiss farmers seek to achieve with cover crops, and the considerations that influence their decision-making. By examining farmers' viewpoints and gaining a deeper understanding of their motivations and challenges, this study aims to uncover new incentives that could encourage greater use of cover crops. These findings could help to shape strategies to further promote the adoption of cover crops, making sustainable farming practices more widespread and appealing. Beyond the role of cover crops, it is also essential to understand how Swiss farmers perceive and respond to climate change, as this knowledge is critical to identify effective ways to encourage sustainable agricultural practices. By linking these two aspects, this research also aims to understand whether farmers see cover crops as a key adaptation measure to cope with climate change, and how they integrate them into their broader climate resilience strategies.

This thesis aims to answer the following research questions:

- I) What considerations are most important for Swiss farmers in cover crop practices?
- II) How do Swiss farmers perceive climate change, and what measures are they taking to adapt?

[Chapter 2](#) provides theoretical background on cover crop types, practice, and its environmental benefits ([Chap. 2.1](#)). An overview of the state of research on cover crop practice is presented ([Chap. 2.2](#)), along with the current legal framework and direct payment system guiding agricultural practices, particularly cover crops ([Chap. 2.3](#)). [Chap. 2.4](#) provides an overview of the impacts of climate change on the agricultural system and the behavioral factors that influence farmers' adaptation and mitigation efforts. [Chapter 3](#) introduces the Q-Methodology, semi-structured interviews, and qualitative content analysis. [Chapter 4](#) presents the results, followed by a discussion and comparison with previous research findings in [Chapter 5](#). Finally, [Chapter 6](#) provides answers to the research questions, highlights the limitations, and suggests areas for further investigation. The conclusion in [Chapter 7](#) summarizes the study.

2 Background and State of the Art

2.1 Cover Crops

Cover crops are grown in between cultivation of two consecutive main crops instead of leaving the soil bare ([Rivière et al., 2022](#)). The practice is mainly applied during autumn and winter as most cash crops have their growing periods in spring and summer ([Shackelford et al., 2019](#)). There are multiple categories of cover crops which address different goals. Often, they are referred as “catch crops” if they should hold back nutrients and prevent nitrate leaching, “green manure” if the primary goal is to increase soil fertility, “fodder” if they are mainly used for livestock, “cover crops” if their primary use is to prevent erosion and have the soil covered. ([Shackelford et al., 2019](#); [Ramírez-García et al., 2015](#)). In this thesis all (“catch crops”, “green manure”, “fodder”, “cover crops”) are grouped under the term cover crops.

There are different motivations to apply cover crop practice. Among them are, benefits for the soil and ecosystem ([Sharma et al., 2018](#)), fodder production ([Pajančić et al., 2009](#)), mitigating and adapting to climate change ([Kaye & Quemada, 2017](#)), and complying with legal regulations ([Agridea, 2024](#)). Depending on the goals in focus it makes sense to choose different cover crop species and mixtures.

Cover crop classes are often distinguished based on plant families ([Rivière et al., 2022](#)). They can be categorized into different main classes: legumes (e.g., alfalfa, vetches, and clovers), non-legumes (e.g., spinach, canola, and flax), grasses (e.g., ryegrass and cereals such as barley), and brassicas (e.g., rapeseed, mustard, radish, and turnip). Sometimes, the classification is refined into gramineous species (grasses), brassicaceous species (Brassicaceae), and leguminous species (Fabaceae) ([Quintarelli et al., 2022](#)). Another common categorization is grasses, legumes, and broadleaf non-legumes ([Kornei 2022](#)). For its simplicity and comprehensiveness, in my thesis the classification of the two main types of cover crops with legumes and non-legumes is used ([Abdalla et al., 2019](#)). Grasses and brassicas are included the in non-legumes class. These distinctions help understand the diverse roles and benefits that different cover crops provide in agricultural systems.

2.1.1 Legumes

Legumes, a large family of flowering plants, offer numerous benefits when used in agricultural landscapes. One of their most significant benefits is their ability to bind atmospheric nitrogen, which enriches the soil and reduces the need for synthetic fertilizers ([Böhm et al., 2020](#)). In addition, legumes play a role in breaking pest cycles and supporting biodiversity ([Böhm et al.,](#)

[2020](#); [Stagnari et al., 2017](#)). Their abundant flowers attract generalist pollinators through extrafloral nectarines, promoting a diverse ecosystem ([Böhm et al., 2020](#)). Furthermore, various legume species, such as different types of clover (e.g., white clover, berseem clover, Persian clover, red clover) and alfalfa, are valuable as animal feed ([Böhm et al., 2020](#)). Their deep taproots also contribute to soil structure by accessing nutrients and water from deeper soil layers ([Siemens, 2020](#)). However, legumes can lead to soil fatigue, a complex of root diseases therefore, respecting crop rotation is crucial ([Fuchs et al., 2023](#)).

Legumes generally have lower carbon-to-nitrogen ratios (C:N) compared to non-legumes ([Adetunji et al., 2020](#)). This means that legumes decompose and release nitrogen more rapidly, benefiting subsequent crops by providing them with readily available nutrients ([Murungu et al., 2011](#)). However, if the nutrients are released before the following crop can utilize them, there is a risk of nutrient leaching ([Murungu et al., 2011](#)).

Despite these benefits, legumes also present some challenges. They tend to produce significantly higher nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions compared to non-legumes ([Abdalla et al., 2019](#)). Increased N leaching and denitrification might also be a problem when choosing legumes ([Büchi et al., 2015](#)). Additionally, the role of legumes in weed suppression is complex. Some legume species are highly competitive and can suppress weeds by affecting the availability of nitrogen, light, and water. However, they provide residual nitrogen benefits that can be favorable to companion flora ([Justes et al., 2012](#)).

The choice of legume species for cover cropping should align with the primary objectives, as different species provide distinct benefits:

The study of Gebhard et al. ([2013](#)) conducted in 2010 and 2011 at Changins Research Station (Nyon) and Rütli Agricultural School (Zollikofen) evaluated 27 legumes as cover crops. Results show that lentil, forage pea, Persian clover, vetch and Egyptian clover demonstrate fast growth rates, particularly evident under dry conditions at Changins in 2010. This highlights their suitability for summer sowing in agricultural systems ([Gebhard et al., 2013](#)). The biomass production is significantly different among species ranging from 0.5 t DM/ha to 5.9 t DM/ha. Some species, such as white lupine, pea, and faba bean, exhibit predominantly vertical growth, while others, like forage pea, lentil, Persian clover, and crimson clover, develop lower but denser foliage ([Gebhard et al., 2013](#)). Biomass production shows a strong correlation with total nitrogen accumulation. The highest values, reaching 163 kg N/ha, were observed in faba bean and hairy vetch. Generally, the N-accumulation consists of approximately 75% fixation from the air and about 25% uptake from the soil ([Gebhard et al., 2013](#)). The effect of weed suppression depends on the amount of biomass produced and the plant growth rate, which

varies among species. For instance, forage pea is highly competitive and can be effective for this purpose ([Gebhard et al., 2013](#)).

2.1.2 Non-legumes

Non-legumes do not fixate nitrogen from the atmosphere like legumes do. Instead, some non-legumes efficiently absorb nitrogen from the soil as they grow ([Thorup-Kristensen, 2006](#)). This ability allows them to prevent nutrient leaching by taking up excess nutrients that would otherwise be washed away below the root zone during rainfall ([Adetunji et al., 2020](#)). Leaching can be reduced by 50% compared to legumes ([Adetunji et al., 2020](#)). In this way, grasses, for example, help retain nutrients and thereby improve soil fertility. Non-legumes are particularly valuable when there is a surplus of readily available nitrogen from previous crops that needs to be absorbed ([Burgenland, 2018](#)). Furthermore, grasses contribute to improve soil hydraulic properties by enhancing soil structure and increasing porosity ([Quintarelli et al., 2022](#)). They are also effective for weed suppression ([White et al., 2016](#)). Generally non-legumes have higher C:N ratios which is beneficial for soil organic matter increase ([Adetunji et al., 2020](#)).

Depending on the goals, different species can be selected. For example, the study by Bodner et al. ([2012](#)) examined the performance of three non-leguminous species—phacelia, rye, and mustard—and the leguminous species vetch in Eastern Austria. This two-year experiment focused on canopy dynamics and root characteristics, leading to the conclusion that rooting patterns varied significantly among species. Phacelia showed the most intense rooting near the soil surface ($L_0 = 9.7 \text{ cm cm}^{-3}$); it was also the most affected by drought, with canopy cover reduced by 41% compared to the others ([Bodner et al., 2012](#)). Vetch allocated more roots to deeper soil layers despite having the lowest L_0 value (4.6 cm cm^{-3}). Mustard demonstrated stable growth across both years, combining high values in maximum canopy cover ($y_{\text{max}} = 76\%$) and surface root density ($L_0 = 6.3 \text{ cm cm}^{-3}$) ([Bodner et al., 2012](#)). Mustard is often used as cover crop ([Agroscope, n.d.](#)). Due to its fast growth rate and requirement of only about 900 growing degree days (GDD), it can be used when the window for cover cropping is relatively short ([Snapp et al., 2005](#)). Additionally, phacelia is a commonly used cover crop ([Agroscope, n.d.](#)). Compared to other species, the price of these seeds is relatively low and it potentially attracts beneficial insects ([Sativa, n.d.](#); [Michel et al., 2020](#)).

This exemplifies how different species vary in their characteristics and highlights the importance of gaining comprehensive knowledge to select the most suitable species based on specific goals and farm conditions.

2.1.3 Cover Crop Mixtures

As explained in [Chapter 2.1](#), choosing between legumes and non-legumes for cover cropping is just one part of the decision-making process. The specific species within these two main groups also have varying ecosystem impacts and may be suitable in different situations. Cover cropping can involve either a single species or a blend of species ([Abdalla et al., 2019](#)). While both legumes and non-legumes can potentially decrease the yield of subsequent main crops, a mixture of legumes and non-legumes has been shown to positively affect yield, increasing it by approximately 13% ([Abdalla et al., 2019](#)).

Higher diversity in cover crop mixtures is associated with a greater range of ecological benefits ([Murrell et al., 2017](#)). Increasing the number of species in a mixture generally enhances the variety of ecosystem services provided ([Loreau et al., 2001](#)). By increasing the number of species, the number of ecosystem benefits is also increased ([Loreau et al., 2001](#)).

Due to competition among species, composition is a critical factor in the success of mixtures. For instance, grasses tend to perform better compared to brassicas, which often underperform ([Murrell et al., 2017](#)). Consequently, seeding rates for grasses in mixtures can be reduced to about 25-50% of the rates used for monocultures ([White et al., 2016](#)). Another strategy involves planting grasses and other high-competition species deeper to give slower-growing species a chance to develop and compete ([Murrell et al., 2017](#)). Additionally, including species with complementary growth periods—both winter-killed and winter-hardy varieties—can maximize ecosystem benefits over a longer time ([White et al., 2016](#)).

The combination of legumes and non-legumes is particularly effective in addressing nitrogen issues ([Dabney et al., 2001](#)). Legumes fix nitrogen from the atmosphere, enriching the soil, while non-legumes absorb soil nitrogen and help to prevent nitrogen leaching. In soils with moderate nitrogen levels, legumes increase nitrogen content, while non-legumes manage excess nitrogen ([White et al., 2016](#)). When soil nitrogen levels are unknown, a mixture of both plant types is ideal, as non-legumes thrive in nitrogen-rich conditions, and legumes excel in nitrogen-poor soils ([White et al., 2016](#)). Grass-legume mixtures offer additional benefits, such as improved root distribution and higher nitrogen fixation compared to monocultures. They are also well-suited for grazing and are valuable in mixed farming systems, especially in regions with crop and livestock farming ([Michel et al., 2020](#)).

However, finding the right balance in a cover crop mixture to maintain or even increase ecosystem benefits compared to monocultures can be challenging ([White et al., 2016](#)). Mixtures may present difficulties in termination and incur higher seed costs compared to monoculture cover crops ([Wolters, 2020](#)).

2.1.4 Termination Methods

The cover crop needs to be terminated before the main crop can properly establish ([Cover Crops Guide, 2024](#)). The timing and method of termination are crucial, as they can significantly impact soil properties and the productivity of the main crop ([Adetunji et al., 2020](#); [Alonso-Ayuso et al., 2020](#)). Improper termination or incorrect timing may result in cover crops becoming weeds themselves, which can compete with the main crop and cause problems ([Wayman et al., 2014](#)). Studies have shown that delayed termination can increase biomass and soil organic matter content, which enhances soil organic carbon and nutrient levels ([Rosario-Lebron & Leslie, 2018](#); [Hirpa, 2013](#)). However, whether this leads to higher yields in the subsequent crop is uncertain ([Hirpa, 2013](#)). Delayed termination often results in increased above-ground biomass and fiber content, offering better soil protection and a slower release of nitrogen ([Alonso-Ayuso et al., 2014](#)). Conversely, early termination reduces the risk of pre-emptive nitrogen competition and allows more time for nitrogen release from cover crop residues ([Alonso-Ayuso et al., 2014](#)). Additionally, early termination of cover crops is easier to manage agronomically and allows for earlier sowing of cash crops ([Bench & Hilshey, 2024](#)). Also, the risk of regrowth and volunteer cover crops is lower in early termination ([Keene et al., 2017](#)).

Termination methods can be broadly categorized into natural, chemical, or mechanical approaches ([Bench & Hilshey, 2024](#)):

The natural method relies on winterkill, where cover crops like oilseed, buckwheat, or sorghum are naturally killed by frost. By the time the cash crop is planted, most winter-killed cover crops are already decomposing. This can delay soil warming and drying in spring ([Bench & Hilshey, 2024](#)).

In the chemical termination method, herbicides are applied to effectively kill cover crops ([Bench & Hilshey, 2024](#)). Application methods vary and can be done before, during, or after the cash crop is planted ([Bench & Hilshey, 2024](#)). Glyphosate is effective for non-legumes, while legumes may require a combination of glyphosate and glufosinate for more thorough control ([Palhano et al., 2018](#)).

The mechanical method includes techniques such as mowing, rolling/crimping, and tillage. Mowing involves cutting the above-ground portion of the cover crop, ideally below the growing point, to ensure effective termination ([Adetunji et al., 2020](#); [Hill & Sprague, 2021](#)). The rolling/crimping method crimps the stems of the cover crop, leading to desiccation and creating a thick mulch layer that decomposes over time ([Bench & Hilshey, 2024](#); [Adetunji et al., 2020](#)). Tillage incorporates the cover crop into the soil ([Alonso-Ayuso et al., 2020](#)). Studies show that rolling/crimping results in higher yields compared to tillage, possibly due to better weed

suppression and improved soil water retention during the early stages of cash crop growth ([Alonso-Ayuso et al., 2020](#)). Additionally, rolling/crimping is considered more environmentally sustainable, as it requires fewer post-emergence operations.

The success of these termination methods can also depend on the cover crop flowering stage. If termination occurs before flowering, the cover crop may continue growing. Waiting too long to terminate increases the risk of the cover crop becoming a volunteer plant in the subsequent crop ([Hill & Sprague, 2021](#)). Additionally, finding an effective termination method can be more challenging with mixtures, as different species may reach their optimal termination stages at different time points ([Adetunji et al., 2020](#)).

2.1.5 Summary

Different cover crop species, termination methods, and timing provide varying environmental benefits and can impact the performance of subsequent cash crops. Effective management practices must be tailored to specific soil conditions, climate conditions, and crop rotation systems ([Abdalla et al., 2019](#)). Selecting the right species, along with appropriate termination methods and timing, is crucial for successful cover cropping and maximizing its benefits within agricultural systems ([Adetunji et al., 2020](#)). These considerations may play an important role in influencing farmers' decisions when adopting cover crop practices. Therefore, it is essential to understand factors such as cover crop species, their ecosystem benefits, and termination strategies. The next subchapter will explore further elements that shape farmers' decision-making in the context of cover crop management.

2.2 State of Research: Farmers and Cover Crop Practice

Most studies on farmer decision-making and behavior aim to understand the reasons behind the adoption or rejection of new practices and technologies ([Rose et al., 2018](#)). Many have explored the factors influencing farmers in their decision-making processes ([Lu et al., 2022](#); [Braito et al., 2020](#); [Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018](#)). Consistently, these studies highlight that farm-specific, personal, social, and economic factors, among others, play crucial roles.

This chapter presents current research on decision-making factors specifically in the context of cover crop practices. The literature is structured into farm-specific factors, personal factors, economic factors, and social factors.

Farm-specific Factors

The type of farming system may influence cover crop adoption ([Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018](#)). Although, no significant differences in cover crop use between certified organic and non-

organic farmers was found ([O'Connell et al., 2014](#)). However, other studies suggest that organic farmers are generally more inclined to invest in cover crops and place greater emphasis on their environmental benefits compared to conventional farmers ([Wayman et al., 2016](#)). Non-adopters often use conventional tillage methods instead of no-till practices, citing concerns about the time required for planting and managing cover crops ([Myers & Wilson, 2023](#)).

Agronomic outcomes and expectations are also critical to cover crop adoption. Farmers are primarily motivated by the potential improvements to soil health. However, specific attributes are valued differently depending on the type of cover crop. For instance, legumes are appreciated for their nitrogen-fixing abilities, while non-legumes are favored for winter hardiness, biomass production, and weed suppression ([Wayman et al., 2016](#)). Despite these benefits, barriers exist. Agronomic concerns, such as disrupting harvesting in the fall or planting schedules in spring, hinder adoption ([Carlisle, 2016](#)). Furthermore, large-scale farmers and those with limited experience in cover crops often face challenges in terminating and incorporating cover crops effectively ([Carlisle, 2016](#)).

Personal Factors

Attitudes play a significant role in the adoption of practices ([Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018](#)). Research indicates that farmers with strong environmental attitudes and a focus on long-term profitability are more likely to adopt cover crops. Conversely, those with short-term, profit-oriented attitudes are less likely to adopt them ([Wang et al., 2020](#)).

Experience also shapes perspectives on cover crops. Interestingly, it is not the farmer's age but rather the duration of farm management experience that influences these views. New practitioners with less than three years of experience tend to view cover crops more positively than more experienced farmers ([O'Connell et al., 2014](#)).

Farmer identity, or how farmers see themselves within a societal context, further influences their management approaches ([Bennett et al., 2023](#); [Thompson et al., 2023](#)). Bennett et al. ([2023](#)) identified two primary farmer identities—*productivist* and *conservationist*—that shape environmental behaviors. *Productivist* farmers focus on maximizing yields and profits and are less likely to adopt cover crops. In contrast, *conservationist* farmers, who prioritize environmental stewardship and land health, are more likely to adopt cover crops, especially when driven by a sense of social responsibility. This is consistent with previous research showing a negative correlation between *productivist* identities and conservation practices, and a positive link between *conservationist* identities and sustainable practices like cover cropping ([Bennett et al., 2023](#)).

Economic Factors

Economic incentives, such as cost-share programs, subsidies, and other conservation initiatives, play a crucial role in encouraging cover crop adoption. These financial supports alleviate farmers' concerns about potential profit losses, reducing significant barriers to adoption ([Bergtold et al., 2017](#)). Additionally, financial rewards, tax breaks, and crop insurance discounts can further motivate farmers to adopt cover crops ([Myers & Wilson, 2023](#)). Surveys indicate that stronger economic incentives and more diverse markets are necessary to drive widespread adoption of cover crops ([Roesch-McNally et al., 2017](#)). Structural and economic barriers, such as crop insurance requirements, also need to be addressed to promote greater use of cover crops. Farmers are more likely to adopt new practices when they believe their profits will remain stable or increase ([Carlisle, 2016](#)). In fact, long-term adopters tend to report increased profitability due to improvements in soil health and experiential learning ([Wang et al., 2020](#)).

While economic factors are vital for overcoming barriers, non-economic factors often play a critical role in decision-making ([Carlisle, 2016](#)).

Social Factors

Social networks have a significant influence on farmers' decisions to adopt new practices ([Bartkowski & Bartke, 2018](#)). Early adopters of cover crops in a region can help facilitate access to infrastructure, equipment, and knowledge for others ([Carlisle, 2016](#)). Peer networks are particularly important for sharing management strategies and best practices, making it easier for others to adopt cover crops. Peer-to-peer knowledge exchange is an effective way to increase cover crop adoption ([Roesch-McNally et al., 2017](#)).

Summary

In summary, while economic incentives and social networks play a pivotal role in facilitating the adoption of cover crops, personal factors such as farmer identities and farm-specific circumstances also significantly influence the decision-making process. A deep understanding of these diverse influences is essential for developing effective policies and programs to promote sustainable agricultural practices. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that even with a thorough understanding of behavioral influences, the inherent unpredictability of complex socio-ecological systems remains ([Bharwani et al., 2005](#)).

Additionally, many studies overlook systemic factors such as social, economic, and political influences, as well as the role of family, advisors, and retailers in the decision-making process ([Rose et al., 2018](#)). While this thesis primarily focuses on farmers as individual decision-makers in cover crop practices, it is acknowledged that this simplification may distort the representation of real-world decision-making.

2.3 Swiss Regulations Concerning Cover Crop Practice

This subchapter is based on Agridea ([2024](#)):

The Confederation is committed to ensuring that the agricultural sector makes a significant contribution to the nation by providing a reliable food supply, preserving natural resources, maintaining rural landscapes, encouraging decentralized settlements, and promoting animal welfare through sustainable, market-oriented production. To achieve these goals, various measures have been introduced.

One such measure, implemented by the Federal Office for Agriculture is the promotion of cover cropping ([BLW, 2023](#)). This practice aims to improve soil fertility while preventing erosion and compaction by maintaining soil cover through methods such as cover crops, green manures, beneficial strips, biodiversity areas, and main crops. Farmers who participate in this program annually receive a subsidy of CHF 200 per hectare ([Agridea, 2024](#)).

Key regulations include:

- All open arable land must be registered, with requirements applied across the entire farm. However, exceptions exist for 20% of the land where these requirements do not need to be met.
- For staggered harvests, the crop is considered harvested once at least half has been gathered. Main crops harvested before October 1st must have soil cover within 7 weeks of harvest. There is no obligation to plant soil cover for crops harvested after September 30th.
- Soil cover must be maintained until February 15th without soil tillage, except for winter crops. Preliminary work for strip-till or strip-seeding before February 15th is permitted under certain conditions, as are certain interventions that keep the root system of the cover crop intact as e.g., grazing or mulching.

2.4 Agriculture in the Context of Climate Change

Climate change is having a significant impact on Swiss agriculture, with projections indicating that these effects will become more pronounced in the future. Accurately attributing specific agricultural changes to climate change is challenging due to the complex interaction of various environmental and socio-economic factors. However, observable trends suggest that rising temperatures may benefit crop yields in cooler, higher-altitude regions. In contrast, reduced summer precipitation in water-scarce areas like Valais and Western Switzerland may negatively affect yields ([Henne et al., 2017](#)). Notably, extreme weather events, rather than gradual changes in average temperature, are typically responsible for most crop losses ([Henne et al., 2017](#)). For example, the summer heatwave of 2003 saw a mean temperature increase of 3.5 °C, which led to a 20% reduction in total crop yield and economic losses amounting to 500 million CHF ([Henne et al., 2017](#); [Grazzini et al., 2003](#)). In addition to direct effects on yields, climate change also indirectly affects agriculture through changes in pest dynamics. Shifts in the timing, range, and behavior of pests pose new challenges, leading to higher production costs ([Henne et al., 2017](#)).

Overall, climate change presents multifaceted and far-reaching challenges to Swiss agriculture. To sustain both profitability and productivity in the sector, adaptation measures are essential ([Tendall & Gaillard, 2015](#)). As the impacts of climate change on Swiss agriculture become increasingly evident, it is crucial to understand not only the environmental and economic consequences but also the human factors that influence responses to these challenges.

2.4.1 Behavioral Factors Influencing Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation

Given the increasing relevance of climate change in agriculture, a growing body of research has begun to explore farmers' behavior in response to climate change ([Kropf & Mitter, 2022](#)). Various behavioral factors either facilitate or hinder the implementation of mitigation and adaptation measures.

These factors can be categorized into cognitive, social, and dispositional elements ([Kropf & Mitter, 2022](#); [Dessart et al., 2019](#)):

Cognitive factors include farmers' perception and thought processes. The way farmers perceive climate change plays an important role in shaping their intentions and actions towards adaptation ([Ricart et al., 2022](#)). Adaptation measures are more likely to be implemented when farmers expect synergies with other desirable outcomes ([Roesch-McNally et al., 2018](#); [Kropf](#)

[& Mitter, 2022](#)). However, perceived trade-offs, such as increased labor demands or costs, can deter adoption ([Kropf & Mitter, 2022](#); [Nicholas & Durham, 2012](#)). Additionally, beliefs about climate change have been found to correlate with adaptation measures ([van Haden et al., 2012](#)), although some studies suggest that these beliefs influence intentions to adapt, but not necessarily the actual implementation of adaptation strategies ([Niles et al., 2016](#)). Emotional responses to climate change risks also shape behavior. To avoid negative emotions, individuals may downplay the importance of climate change, leading to its neglect and a subsequent lack of adaptation efforts. This emotional avoidance can act as a significant barrier to long-term adaptation ([Kropf & Mitter, 2022](#)).

Social factors, particularly relationships with others, also play a crucial role. Being part of professional networks, interacting with peers, and maintaining personal connections can significantly influence both adaptation and mitigation behaviors ([Niles et al., 2016](#); [Kropf & Mitter, 2022](#)). Farmers who regularly share information and experiences with their peers are more inclined to adopt new practices and implement innovative measures.

Dispositional factors refer to personal characteristics such as the farmer's connection to their region and farm, their perceived moral obligation to act, and their underlying value systems. These factors strongly influence adaptation and mitigation behaviors. Additionally, the farming attitude plays a crucial role in how farmers respond to climate change ([Kropf & Mitter, 2022](#)). For example, farmers with *conservative* attitudes tend to favor agronomic measures, while those with a more *productivist* attitude are more likely to adopt financial measures and exhibit opportunity-seeking behavior in the context of climate change adaptation ([Käyhkö, 2019](#); [Kropf & Mitter, 2022](#)).

Overall, these behavioral factors highlight the complex interplay between cognition, social influence, and personal values in shaping farmers' responses to climate change.

2.4.2 Climate Change Perception and Adaptation

Farmers' perceptions of climate change significantly shape their intentions and decisions regarding the implementation of adaptive measures ([Kropf & Mitter, 2022](#); [Ricart et al., 2022](#)). Many farmers have reported experiencing notable shifts and anomalies in local weather patterns over recent decades ([Brüssow et al., 2019](#); [Ricart et al., 2022](#)). The impact of climate change on agriculture is closely tied to geographical factors. Ricart et al.'s ([2023](#)) comprehensive review analyzed 108 studies from diverse global regions, providing a broad perspective on both the effects of climate change and the strategies for adaptation. The main

climate change impacts perceived across various countries include rising and extreme temperatures, shifting rainfall patterns, and increasing drought ([Ricart et al., 2023](#)).

Eleven key climate change adaptation measures have been identified, with three emerging as particularly significant ([Ricart et al., 2023](#)):

Introducing new crop varieties that are more resistant to heat and less vulnerable to emerging pests; Altering cropping patterns, such as incorporating cover crops or adjusting sowing dates; Promoting water and soil conservation techniques, including rainwater harvesting. These findings are consistent with an earlier review of 45 studies, where the most commonly applied strategies were the introduction of new crop varieties and the adjustment of planting dates ([Ricart et al., 2022](#)). In total, 16 main measures were identified and grouped into five distinct categories (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Key Climate Change Adaptation Measures (Ricart et al., 2022)

The reviewed literature clearly shows that farmers have a stronger emphasis on adaptation measures compared to mitigation efforts. This difference in focus may be because adaptation is typically seen as a private endeavor while mitigation is considered more of a public responsibility ([Kropf & Mitter, 2022](#)).

3 Methods

This chapter outlines the methods used to address the research questions presented in [Chapter 1](#). A mixed method approach, combining Q-Methodology ([Chapter 3.2](#)) and semi-structured interviews ([Chapter 3.3](#)), was employed to investigate the two key research questions.

Q-Methodology (see [Chapter 3.2.1](#)) was specifically chosen to explore research question I, as cover crops serve a variety of purposes—such as soil improvement, erosion control, and fodder— which suggests that farmers may hold differing viewpoints on cover crop practices. Q-Methodology was employed because it is suitable for qualitatively and quantitatively capturing and analyzing participants' subjective views. To systematically capture this, farmers (see P-Set in [Chapter 3.2.3](#)) were asked to rank a series of predefined statements (see Q-Set in [Chapter 3.2.2](#)) related to cover crop practices. These rankings were then analyzed (see [Chapter 3.2.5](#)) using factor analysis to identify shared viewpoints among participants. In addition to the Q-Sort ([Chapter 3.2.4](#)), participants explained rankings, offering deeper insights into their individual viewpoints. This approach led to a more comprehensive understanding of the diverse views farmers have regarding cover crop practices.

For research question II, semi-structured interviews provided the depth and flexibility needed to explore complex issues, such as farmers' views on climate change, allowing for a richer qualitative understanding. The focus of research question II was not primarily on identifying contrasting viewpoints, but rather on understanding the farmers' perceptions of climate change and the range of adaptation measures they are implementing in response. Within the same interview, after the Q-Methodology section, participants were therefore asked additional questions about climate change in a semi-structured format (see [3.3.1](#)). These interviews were transcribed (see [3.3.2](#)) and analyzed using Mayring's qualitative content analysis (see [3.3.3](#)), which helped uncover key themes and patterns.

Finally, participants completed a survey to collect demographic data ([Chapter 3.1](#)), adding further context to the findings.

3.1 Survey

To systematically collect key data and provide a clear, comparable overview of participants, a structured questionnaire is essential. In research, demographic questions are crucial for gathering background information about participants, which enhances the interpretation of results and allows for a comprehensive analysis ([Dobosh, 2017](#)). Standard demographic questions typically include variables such as age, gender, educational background, and employment status ([Dobosh, 2017](#)). For this thesis, a standard survey from Bütikofer et al. ([2023](#)) has been utilized to ensure comparability with other findings of the research group. Specific questions about cover crops were incorporated into the standardized survey ([Appendix E](#)). The results of this survey, including participant demographics and characteristics, are detailed in [Chapter 3.2.3](#) where the set of participants is described.

3.2 Q-Methodology

To ensure comprehensive coverage of all essential aspects in this chapter, I utilized the checklist developed by Dieteren et al. ([2023](#)) as a guiding framework.

3.2.1 Overview

Q-Methodology, originally developed by psychologist William Stephenson ([1935](#)), has been applied across various fields, including social sciences, psychology, and agriculture ([Sneegas et al., 2021](#)). Recently, the recognition and acceptance of this methodology have significantly increased ([Müller & Kals, 2004](#); [Dieteren et al., 2023](#)). The primary objective of Q-Methodology is to capture subjective perspectives and assess them quantitatively. By using statistical techniques such as correlation and factor analysis, Q-Methodology facilitates the quantitative examination of social phenomena, enabling the comparison and clustering of individual viewpoints ([McKeown & Thomas, 2013](#)). For example, farmers' differing points of view regarding their goals in cover crop practice can be uncovered and characterized.

Q-Methodology involves four main stages ([Zabala et al., 2018](#)):

The initial stage involves developing the research design and defining the Q-Set and P-Set. The Q-Set is a subsample of the discourse, derived from literature, qualitative interviews, and expert assessments ([Zabala et al., 2018](#)). The P-Set is usually non-randomly chosen, with Watts and Stenner ([2012](#)) recommending 40-60 participants to ensure representativeness. They also recommend having fewer participants than statements. To sustain a good Q-Methodological study it is not necessary to have large numbers of participants ([Watts &](#)

[Stenner, 2012](#)). Research shows that typical Q-Studies have between 24 and 46 participants ([Sneegas et al., 2021](#); [Zabala et al., 2018](#)). Then participants selected according to a predefined guideline are recruited for the study ([Zabala et al., 2018](#)).

The subsequent step is data collection. During participant interviews, it is crucial to adhere to a systematic procedure. The Q-Set, which consists of predefined statements, is presented to the participants, who are required to rank these statements according to their personal preferences, ranging from "very unimportant" to "very important" ([Zabala et al., 2018](#)). Participants arrange the statements on a provided grid. The grid's structure, which determines whether the number of statements per column is fixed or flexible, depends on whether a forced normal distribution is used, which is optional but commonly applied ([Zabala et al., 2018](#); [Watts & Stenner, 2012](#)). This arrangement is then recorded and digitized. To ensure a thorough understanding of the participants' viewpoints and to facilitate accurate categorization, participants are systematically asked to elaborate on specific aspects of their rankings ([Watts & Stenner, 2012](#)). Typically, they are asked to explain why they placed certain statements in the most extreme columns ([Zabala et al., 2018](#)).

Following this process, the data undergoes both quantitative and qualitative analysis. A by-person factor analysis is conducted to identify patterns in the data ([Brown, 1980](#); [Watts & Stenner, 2012](#)). The number of factors is determined using statistical methods such as the Kaiser criterion (Kaiser-Guttman rule) ([Zabala et al., 2018](#); [Kaiser, 1960](#)). For determining the number of factors, it is additionally useful to integrate qualitative data, as it helps assess whether new factors reveal meaningful distinctions or nuances among groups based on interviews and participant impressions. Factors are then rotated using techniques such as varimax to maximize the explained variance. Thereby it can be assured that each Q-Sort has a strong loading on a single factor ([Watts & Stenner, 2012](#)).

In the final step, the factor loadings and z-scores, which are the products of the analysis, are interpreted. Z-scores reveal the relative importance of each statement within the factors, while factor loadings indicate the strength of each participant's association with those factors ([Watts & Stenner, 2012](#); [Zabala et al., 2018](#)). Distinguishing and consensus statements are identified based on the z-scores ([Zabala & Pascual, 2016](#)). By integrating both quantitative data (z-scores and factor loadings) and qualitative insights, a comprehensive narrative is developed that captures the diverse and nuanced viewpoints of the participants.

3.2.2 Q-Set

After reviewing the relevant methodological literature ([Watts & Stenner, 2012](#); [Zabala et al., 2018](#); [Sneegas et al., 2021](#); [Dieteren et al., 2023](#)), I began developing the Q-Set. The goal was to create a comprehensive set of statements related to cover crop practices, focusing on key aspects such as goals, challenges, and influencing factors. These statements were framed around the guiding question:

“In cover crop practice, it is important to me that...”

The statements for the Q-Set were derived from literature. Typically, a Q-Set includes between 40 and 80 statements ([Shinebourne, 2009](#)). However, given the specific focus on cover crop practices, only 22 relevant statements were identified. The collection process was concluded once no additional relevant statements emerged, following the principle of data saturation ([Lee, 2017](#)).

The statements were reviewed and reformulated within our research group to ensure consistency in wording ([Watts & Stenner, 2012](#)). Prior to conducting the interviews, the Q-Set was validated by a cover crop expert ([Brown, 2004](#)). This validation took place through a telephone discussion, during which the expert reviewed the statements. The expert suggested one additional statement, which was incorporated into the Q-Set. The revised set of statements was then presented to the expert in written form once again, and the expert confirmed that the Q-Set was complete (Table 1). With the Q-Set finalized, I proceeded to recruit participants for the study.

Statements

In cover crop practice, it is important to me that...	Sources
1 ...the cover crop reduces pests and diseases in the subsequent crop	Adetunji et al. (2020); Lu et al. (2007)
2 ...the cover crop cultivation causes minimal costs	Snapp et al. (2005)
3 ...the cover crop leads to a lower need for inputs (fertilizers, pesticides)	O'Reilly et al. (2012); Dabney et al. (2001)
4 ...the cover crop has a high crop rotation compatibility	Chapagain et al. (2020)
5 ...the cover crop is well-suited for late sowing	Anugroho et al. (2009); Liebig et al. (2015)
6 ...the cover crop causes few problems with volunteer plants	Wayman et al. (2014)
7 ...the cover crop cultivation requires only minimal labor	Kropf & Mitter (2022); Nicholas & Durham (2012)
8 ...the cover crop meets legal requirements	BLW (2023); Agridea (2024)
9 ...the cover crop increases the yields of the subsequent crop	Finney & Kaye (2016)
10 ...the cover crop promotes biodiversity	Murrell et al. (2017)
11 ...the cover crop helps to attract and sustain beneficial insects	Murrell et al. (2017); Koudahe et al. (2022)
12 ...the cover crop looks neat and well-maintained	Burns (2021)
13 ...the cover crop returns nutrients to the soil	Adetunji et al. (2020)
14 ...the cover crop suppresses weeds	Adetunji et al. (2020); Finney & Kaye (2016)
15 ...the cover crop reduces soil temperature fluctuations	Interview with Cover Crop Expert
16 ...the cover crop helps prevent groundwater contamination	Clark (2007)
17 ...the cover crop contributes to climate protection	Adetunji et al. (2020); Koudahe et al. (2022)
18 ...the cover crop maintains soil moisture	Adetunji et al. (2020); Lu et al. (2007)
19 ...the cover crop can be used as fodder	Gabriel et al. (2013); Vujic et al. (2021)
20 ...the cover crop facilitates field trafficability in spring	Odhiambo & Bomke (2007)
21 ...the cover crop loosens the soil	Daryanto et al. (2018); Koudahe et al. (2022)
22 ...the cover crop reduces soil erosion	Wolters (2020); White et al. (2016)
23 ...the cover crop promotes humus formation	Wolters (2020)

Table 1: Validated Q-Set consisting of 23 statements. Statements refer to introduced sentence above.

3.2.3 P-Set

Based on the recommended participant numbers ([Zabala et al., 2018](#); [Sneegas et al., 2021](#); [Dieteren et al., 2023](#)), the study aimed to include 25-30 participants. To explore shared viewpoints on cover crop practices, farmers were recruited to participate in the Q-Sort ([Younas et al., 2024](#)).

To facilitate participant recruitment within the limited timeframe of a master's thesis, our research group decided to impose minimal selection criteria. The criteria were: 1) participants must be actively engaged in cover crop practices and 2) they must be German-speaking and located in the Swiss Plateau (Figure 2). Capturing the viewpoint of the primary decision-maker is essential for this research. Therefore, 3) participants were required to be the main decision-makers on their farms regarding cover crop practices.

Figure 2: Geographic distribution of P-Set on the Swiss Plateau. Red dots represent interviewed farmers.

To capture a broad spectrum of viewpoints, including a diverse group of participants was essential ([Seghezzo et al., 2023](#)). This consideration guided the purposive sampling process. The directory "[Hofsuche](#)", which contains data on 3,553 farmers, offered not only contact information but also details about crop types and farming practices (e.g., conventional, IP-Suisse, organic). This information was crucial for selecting a diverse group of farmers, thereby representing a wide range of perspectives.

Initially, 10 farmers were contacted via email, but only one response was received within a week. Consequently, the recruitment strategy was adjusted to telephone contact, which proved to be significantly more effective. Of approximately 60 farmers contacted by phone, over 25 agreed to participate in an interview. Common reasons for non-participation included limited time availability and the lack of cover crop practices on their farms. Additionally, following each interview, participants were asked to refer other potential participants. Through this snowball sampling method, five additional farmers were recruited for the study ([Naderifar et al., 2017](#)).

The P-Set included 30 participants, with 29 identifying as male and 1 as female. All participants primarily managed their farms, though most also work outside the farm. Ten farms are certified organic, one was unofficially organic. Due to size (< 1 ha), it did not meet the formal requirements of a certified farm. Three participants stated they were partly organic, either in transition or meeting most organic criteria. Sixteen farms followed conventional practices. The average farm size was 37 ha (range: 0.9 ha to 110 ha), with an average of 24 ha dedicated to crop cultivation (range: 0.9 ha to 85 ha), representing about 70% of the total land. Participants' ages ranged from 29 to 65 years, with an average age of 44 years. Educational backgrounds varied, with 1 participant lacking agricultural education and 5 holding agricultural university degrees. The average livestock unit (LSU) was 48, ranging from 0 to 400 LSU. These demographic characteristics reflected substantial diversity, meeting the selection criteria outlined ([Seghezzo et al., 2023](#)).

3.2.4 Data Collection Q-Sort

Data collection was conducted between the 2nd of May 2024 and the 31st of May 2024. Typically, one or two interviews were conducted per day. All interviews were conducted on-site at the participants' farms. To reach the farms, I utilized public transport, my bicycle, or walked, with an average travel time of 1 hour and 30 minutes one way. Conducting interviews at the participants' farms was suggested to ensure comfort and accurate responses ([Elwood & Martin, 2010](#)). Additionally, minimizing the participants' effort was a key consideration. The predominantly rainy weather in May 2024 facilitated scheduling, as it reduced outdoor farm activities and allowed greater availability for interviews. However, three interviews were rescheduled due to favorable weather conditions, which led farmers to take advantage of brief opportunities for fieldwork. On average, the interviews lasted 50 minutes, with the longest lasting 1 hour and 30 minutes, and the shortest lasting 30 minutes. Prior to the interview, it was essential to ensure that participants comprehended the study's purpose and procedures ([Manti & Licari, 2018](#)). They were provided with explanation of their rights, including the confidentiality of their responses and their right to withdraw from the study at any point.

Additionally, participants were asked to sign a consent form, confirming their understanding and agreement to the recording of the interview (compare [Appendix F](#)).

The interviews followed a structured procedure based on a predefined guideline. It was mainly structured in four parts:

In the initial “opening” segment, participants were asked about their farms and personal experiences, adhering to the interview guidelines established by Bütikofer et al. (2023). To tailor the study's focus, context-specific questions about cover crops were incorporated. The duration of this segment varied significantly among participants, with the longest lasting 43 minutes.

In the subsequent and core segment of the interview, farmers were asked to sort 23 Q-Statements based on their importance. They were consistently instructed to make decisions spontaneously, reflecting what was important to them and their farms. Initially, statements were categorized into three groups: important, neutral, and unimportant, with the important pile typically being the largest ([Watts & Stenner, 2012](#)). Participants then arranged the statements on a grid designed to follow a normal distribution, with predefined rows for placing the statements (Figure 3). The sorting process started with the least important statements, proceeded to the most important, and then addressed the neutral statements. Some participants commented on their choices. After sorting, participants were given the opportunity to make any final adjustments before a photograph was taken of the final arrangement. Only a few farmers made additional changes.

To ensure a comprehensive understanding of participants' viewpoints, a Q-Reflection was conducted. Participants were asked to explain the reasoning behind the placement of their two most and two least important statements. They were also queried about any significant statements they believed were missing and which statements they found most challenging to sort along with the reasons for these difficulties.

In the last part of the interview questions about climate change were asked for the methodological procedure of this part consider [Chapter 3.3](#).

Figure 3: Q-Sort grid following a normal distribution. Ranking from least important (-3) to most important (+3).

3.2.5 Q-Analysis

The first step in the analysis involved digitizing the data into an Excel spreadsheet. Each statement was assigned a score ranging from -3 (least important) to +3 (most important). To verify the accuracy of digitization, the average score of all rows (Q-Sorts) was calculated and confirmed to be zero, as the data is following a normal distribution ([Nadarajah, 2011](#)).

Following digitization, the next phase involved performing a factor analysis to identify patterns and shared viewpoints among participants ([Previte et al., 2007](#)). Q-Methodology considers participants as variables rather than items, enabling a by-person factor analysis that highlights commonalities and differences in individual viewpoints ([Brown, 1980](#); [Watts & Stenner, 2012](#)). For the analysis of Q-Methodology data, specialized software is recommended to perform factor analysis and interpret the results. While PQMethod software is commonly used for this purpose, KADE was chosen for its better accessibility and user-friendly interface ([Dieteren et al., 2023](#)).

At this stage, three participants were excluded from the analysis. Two were removed due to their engagement in under sowing practices, which were not intended for inclusion in this study and could lead to differing interpretations of the Q-Statements. One participant was excluded for being unable to differentiate between statements within the forced normal distribution grid, finding too many statements equally important. After these exclusions, a correlation matrix was created to identify preliminary connections within the data ([Hadavand-Siri & Deutsch, 2012](#)).

Selecting the right factors is a crucial part of the analysis process, and it demands careful consideration ([Coogan & Herrington, 2011](#)). First, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted ([Zabala et al., 2018](#)). Eight eigenvalues exceeded 1, indicating, according to the Kaiser-Guttman criterion ([Kaiser, 1960](#)), that these factors explain a significant amount of variance in the data. While this criterion is useful, it is not the sole to consider. Ultimately up to 8 factors were considered.

Scree Plot

Figure 4: Scree plot showing eigenvalues for factor selection (KADE)

Subsequently, the graph (Figure 4) was examined, revealing an elbow point that suggested an optimal number of 5 factors ([Cattell, 1966](#)). This method involves identifying where the plot of eigenvalues changes sharply, indicating a diminishing return for additional factors. A flat slope beyond this point suggests additional factors are likely random and not meaningful ([Ledesma et al., 2015](#)). Further analysis assessed whether at least 10% of the variance could be explained by each factor ([Sneegas et al., 2021](#)). Factor 5 did not meet this criterion and was excluded. Based on the statistical findings, it was determined that either 2, 3 or 4 factors were viable options.

In Q-Analysis, integrating qualitative considerations is essential ([Coogan & Herrington, 2011](#)). Therefore, comprehensive factor analyses were conducted for 2, 3, and 4 factors. The results were carefully analyzed and interpreted with reference to participant-specific information. With only 2 factors, the primary distinction was whether cover crops were viewed as fodder or green manure. This was highlighted by the Q-Statement regarding fodder (Q-Statement 19), which had a Q-Sort value of -3 for one factor ($p < 0.0001$) and +3 for the other factor ($p < 0.0001$).

Given the numerous points influencing farmers' decisions about cover cropping, limiting the analysis to 2 factors would result in the loss of valuable information.

Thus, a comprehensive analysis was conducted for 3 and 4 factors. Qualitative data from interviews and questionnaires enriched the interpretation of the factor analysis results, aiding in the determination of the appropriate number of factors to retain. Employing qualitative data aimed to ensure robust and reliable identification of shared viewpoints and patterns among participants ([Coogan & Herrington, 2011](#)). Ultimately, the decision was made to focus on 3 factors. This decision was made because, with 4 factors, the 4th factor had only one significant distinguishing statement (5: +1) at $p < 0.01$ and lacked a coherent narrative. Consequently, the analysis proceeded with 3 factors.

Rotation can be performed using either judgmental (manual) rotation or varimax rotation, both of which maintain orthogonal (perpendicular) axes ([Watts & Stenner, 2012](#)). Varimax rotation is particularly useful as it maximizes explained variance. Thereby it ensures that each Q-Sort, which represents how a participant ranked the statements, has a strong loading on only one single factor ([Watts & Stenner, 2012](#)). After rotation, the factor loading of each Q-Sort is examined. Factor loadings quantify how strongly a Q-Sort is related to a specific factor ([Brown, 2004](#)). In this analysis, a significance threshold of $p < 0.01$ was used to identify which Q-Sorts align with each factor ([Kline, 1994](#)). Q-Sorts that show a significant correlation with a factor get flagged. This makes it possible to determine which participants are associated with a specific viewpoint.

One participant demonstrated a significant negative loading on the relevant factor suggesting a divergence from the factor's viewpoint and was consequently excluded from further analysis by removing the flagging ([Brown, 2004](#)). After this step the analysis was done, and the data was sent to output. At this stage, KADE presents the results in a well-structured and easily understandable format.

The results are presented by KADE in a table showing z-scores, which indicate the average level of (dis)agreement that each factor expresses with regard to the corresponding statement. The z-scores represent the weighted average of scores assigned to a statement by similar respondents ([Zabala et al., 2018](#)). They represent how a hypothetical individual, embodying a group of similar respondents (the factor), would rank the statements ([Zabala et al., 2018](#)). Z-scores help determine whether a statement is a point of consensus across all factors or distinguishes one factor from the others. Statements with statistically relevant similar z-scores across factors are considered consensus statements, while those with differing z-scores are distinguishing statements ([Zabala & Pascal, 2016](#)). The distinguishing statement thresholds were set at $p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$ to identify significant differences between the factor groups.

In the KADE software, a table of distinguishing statements can be generated, along with hypothetical composites for each factor ([Appendix A](#)). Composites are essentially idealized Q-Sorts that represent the typical ranking patterns for each factor, highlighting the statements that participants within a factor find more or less important. This offers insights into the different viewpoints represented by the factors. Integrating quantitative data, such as z-scores and factor loadings, with qualitative data aids in developing narratives, thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of diverse viewpoints ([Coogan & Herrington, 2011](#)).

3.3 Semi-Structured Interview and Content Analysis

3.3.1 Interview

In addition to the Q-Methodology, semi-structured interviews were selected as a data collection method. To address the research questions, a set of open, relatively general questions was predefined ([Donalek, 2005](#); [Niebert & Groppengiesser, 2013](#)). This approach allows the researcher to explore emerging topics during the dialogue, thereby increasing the depth and relevance of the data collected ([DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree, 2006](#)). For research question II, 3-4 predefined questions were asked, supplemented by follow-up questions to delve deeper into the participants' responses and ensure a comprehensive understanding of their perspectives (compare [Appendix C](#)).

3.3.2 Transcripts

Transcription involves converting verbal and potentially non-verbal communication from audio data into text ([Kuckartz et al., 2013](#)). The subsequent analysis emphasizes manifest content rather than communicative-interactional aspects or latent meanings. Therefore, a straightforward transcription method was employed ([Mey, 2023](#)). Paralinguistic features were not included. The transcripts were anonymized to exclude sensitive personal information about the participants ([Medjedović, 2022](#)).

3.3.3 Content Analysis

To analyze the interview data, Mayring's qualitative content analysis method was utilized. The interview transcripts, comprising over 430 pages, were imported into MAXQDA, a qualitative data analysis software. Given the extensive length of the transcripts, the structuring technique of content analysis was selected, as it focuses on extracting specific aspects from the material ([Mayring, 2015](#)).

An inductive approach was adopted for the analysis to identify themes and patterns, allowing categories to emerge naturally from the data ([Ruin, 2017](#)). This approach enabled the derivation of themes and categories directly from the data, facilitating a nuanced understanding of participants' perspectives without relying on preconceived notions. Statements were systematically reviewed to identify recurring themes and patterns, leading to the development of initial codes based on observed commonalities.

In content analysis, it is essential to predefine the analytical units, abstraction level, selection criteria, and the analysis question ([Mayring, 2015](#)).

For this study, the coding unit, which represents the smallest unit of material for analysis and categorization, was defined as a sentence. Conversely, the contextual unit represents the largest text segment within which the meaning of a coding unit can be fully understood. This is important because individual sentences might be misunderstood when taken out of context. To address this, it is suggested to define the entire interview as the contextual unit, ensuring that the meaning of a sentence or phrase is accurately interpreted within the broader context of the conversation ([Mayring, 2015](#)). Those choices were made to align with the focus on content rather than communicative-interactional aspects or latent meanings, where individual word analysis might be more pertinent ([Stemler, 2015](#)).

For this research, a high level of abstraction was chosen to identify overarching themes and patterns in the data related to climate change perception and adaptation. Instead of coding very specific details, participants' statements were grouped into broadly defined categories, such as "perception of climate change indicators" or "adaptation strategies". This approach allowed for the identification of general trends and commonalities in the responses, providing a comprehensive understanding of the key themes surrounding climate change perception and adaptation ([Mayring, 2015](#)).

Selection criteria play a central role in qualitative content analysis, as they determine which text segments are deemed relevant and included in the analysis ([Mayring, 2015](#)). In this case, only statements related to climate change were included, while statements without any reference to climate change were not considered.

The following analysis question was pre-defined:

What specific indicators, challenges, opportunities, adaptation strategies and emotional responses do farmers describe in relation to climate change?

This question is closely aligned with the overarching research question, ensuring that the coding process remains focused on the key aspects of the study's objectives. This approach facilitates the identification of relevant patterns and themes within the data.

In the initial step, sections of the transcripts relevant to the research question II were highlighted. The export of these highlighted excerpts from MAXQDA included annotations for identifying the participants. This resulted in a new document consisting of 88 pages of relevant excerpts, which was then re-imported into MAXQDA for further analysis. At this stage, only the relevant data for analysis was retained in MAXQDA, with all other information excluded. Following this, an inductive category-building process was conducted in MAXQDA, where categories were defined, categorization rules were established, and representative statements were identified. Once the categorized statements were finalized, they were exported to Excel for a subsequent round of analysis. During this phase, the categories were carefully reviewed to assess whether any needed to be separated or consolidated, ensuring that all statements were accurately categorized and aligned within their respective categories. After finalizing this review, the coding framework was completed. It was then applied to the entire dataset to ensure that all statements were correctly categorized and appropriately coded according to the established guidelines (compare [Appendix D](#)).

4 Results

4.1 Statistical Analysis

Correlations between Factor Scores

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
Factor 1	1	0.3632	0.2107
Factor 2	0.3632	1	0.2128
Factor 3	0.2107	0.2128	1

Table 2: Correlation matrix of factor scores

The results of the analysis show that 55% of the study variance can be explained by three factors. The correlations between these factors are weak (Table 2). Factor 3 has a low correlation with factors 1 and 2 (correlation < 0.3), while factors 1 and 2 have a medium correlation with each other ([Kuckartz et al., 2013](#)).

Factor 1 is defined by 12 variables, factor 2 by 8 variables, and factor 3 by 2 variables. The defining variables indicate how many Q-Sorts loaded significantly at $p < 0.01$ ([Zabala & Pascal, 2016](#)). The Q-Sorts that did not load significantly on any factor are P2, P5, P18, and P29 (P stands for participant). Additionally, P6 was excluded due to a negative factor loading (-0.677), indicating an opposite attitude to factor 3. Factor loadings represent how much a respondent correlates with a factor ([Zabala et al., 2018](#)). All factor loadings in our study exceeded the threshold of 0.54, signifying a robust association with their respective factors ([Kuckartz et al., 2013](#)). Specifically, the lowest factor loading observed was 0.5443, corresponding to Q-Sort P8 on factor 2 (Table 3).

Q-Sort	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
P 17	<u>0.8034</u>	0.2754	0.2614
P 21	<u>0.7809</u>	0.2294	-0.3223
P 16	<u>0.7655</u>	-0.0041	-0.1584
P 25	<u>0.7602</u>	0.1126	0.2609
P 19	<u>0.7563</u>	0.1983	-0.0069
P 3	<u>0.7286</u>	0.2566	0.3007
P 9	<u>0.6918</u>	0.1325	0.2583
P 23	<u>0.6581</u>	0.0589	0.4148
P 10	<u>0.6546</u>	-0.1054	0.2883
P 15	<u>0.6262</u>	0.2487	-0.1047
P 22	<u>0.6108</u>	0.0233	-0.2283
P 4	<u>0.5899</u>	0.4909	-0.213
P 5	0.2791	-0.1993	-0.1779
P 14	0.1076	<u>0.7829</u>	0.0922
P 1	0.326	<u>0.7643</u>	0.1151
P 11	0.049	<u>0.7217</u>	0.0579
P 28	0.0549	<u>0.7053</u>	-0.3271
P 7	0.1196	<u>0.668</u>	-0.4941
P 27	0.0436	<u>0.5852</u>	0.1579
P 26	0.0197	<u>0.576</u>	0.312
P 8	0.0956	<u>0.5443</u>	-0.0779
P 18	0.1546	0.5056	0.276
P 30	0.1192	0.1962	<u>0.7653</u>
P 12	0.0256	0.329	<u>0.691</u>
P 6	0.1084	0.1753	-0.6778
P 2	0.4374	0.2647	0.4753
P 29	0.4587	-0.2283	0.4598

Table 3: Factor loadings of Q-Sorts showing participant correlations with the three factors. The flagged Q-Sorts are underlined and bold.

The z-score describes the average level of (dis)agreement that a factor expresses with a given statement ([Zabala et al., 2018](#)). It also reflects the extent to which a hypothetical individual within the same factor group would prioritize the statement ([Zabala et al., 2018](#)). These z-scores can be converted back into the rankings ranging from -3 to +3, as illustrated in Table 4.

No.	Statement	Factors		
		1	2	3
	In cover crop practice, it is important to me that...			
1	...the cover crop reduces pests and diseases in the subsequent crop	0	1	-2
2	...the cover crop cultivation causes minimal costs	-2	0	-3
3*	...the cover crop leads to a lower need for inputs (fertilizers, pesticides)	0	0	-1
4	...the cover crop has high crop rotation compatibility	1	1	-2
5*	...the cover crop is well-suited for late sowing	-2	-2	-3
6	...the cover crop causes few problems with volunteer plants	1	2	-1
7	...the cover crop cultivation requires only minimal labor	-1	0	-2
8	...the cover crop meets legal requirements	-2	-2	0
9*	...the cover crop increases the yields of the subsequent crop	1	1	0
10*	...the cover crop promotes biodiversity	0	-1	1
11	...the cover crop helps attract and sustain beneficial insects	0	-2	-1
12	...the cover crop looks neat and well-maintained	-3	-3	0
13	...the cover crop returns nutrients to the soil	3	3	0
14	...the cover crop suppresses weeds	2	2	-1
15*	...the cover crop reduces soil temperature fluctuations	-1	-1	0
16	...the cover crop helps prevent groundwater contamination	-1	-1	1
17	...the cover crop contributes to climate change mitigation	0	-3	1
18	...the cover crop maintains soil moisture	1	2	1
19	...the cover crop can be used as fodder	-3	3	3
20	...the cover crop facilitates field trafficability in spring	-1	0	2
21	...the cover crop loosens the soil	2	0	2
22	...the cover crop reduces soil erosion	2	-1	2
23	...the cover crop promotes humus formation	3	1	3

*Consensus statements are marked with asterisk

Table 4: Rankings of cover crop statements across three factors. *Consensus statements are marked with asterisk.

Statements in the study can be categorized as either consensus or distinguishing based on their z-scores. Consensus statements exhibit similar z-scores across all three factors, not exceeding a specific threshold. This threshold is determined by multiplying the standard error of the z-score differences between pairs of factors by 1.96, reflecting a significance level of $p < 0.05$ (Zabala et al., 2018; Zabala & Pascal, 2016). These consensus statements indicate a common agreement among the factors (Brown, 1980; Zabala & Pascal, 2016). Conversely, distinguishing statements have z-scores that significantly differ from those of other factors, surpassing the threshold value. These distinguishing statements highlight the unique aspects within each factor, helping to identify how different viewpoints diverge (Zabala & Pascal, 2016).

Examining both consensus and distinguishing statements is crucial for a comprehensive interpretation of the viewpoints. Consensus statements identify areas of broad agreement

across various viewpoints, while distinguishing statements highlight the unique aspects that define each viewpoint. This dual analysis enriches the understanding of the underlying dimensions and nuances in the study (Zabala et al., 2018). The distinguishing statements are detailed in Table 5 and the consensus statements are marked with asterisk in Table 4.

Factor 1

Threshold	Z-score	Q Sort Value	No.	Statement
P < 0.05	-0.05	0	1	...the cover crop reduces pests and diseases in the subsequent crop
P < 0.005	-0.88	-2	2	...the cover crop cultivation causes minimal costs
P < 0.05	0.74	1	4	...the cover crop has a high crop rotation compatibility
P < 0.0001	-2.18	-3	19	...the cover crop can be used as fodder

Factor 2

Threshold	Z-score	Q Sort Value	No.	Statement
P < 0.05	0.4	1	1	...the cover crop reduces pests and diseases in the subsequent crop
P < 0.0005	-0.06	0	2	...the cover crop cultivation causes minimal costs
P < 0.05	0.27	1	4	...the cover crop has a high crop rotation compatibility
P < 0.05	-0.28	0	7	...the cover crop cultivation requires only minimal labor
P < 0.05	-1.03	-2	11	...the cover crop helps attract and sustain beneficial insects
P < 0.0001	-1.25	-3	17	...the cover crop contributes to climate protection
P < 0.05	1.1	2	18	...the cover crop maintains soil moisture
P < 0.01	0.26	0	21	...the cover crop loosens the soil
P < 0.0001	-0.38	-1	22	...the cover crop reduces soil erosion
P < 0.001	0.62	1	23	...the cover crop promotes humus formation

Factor 3

Threshold	Z-score	Q Sort Value	No.	Statement
P < 0.0005	-1.34	-2	1	...the cover crop reduces pests and diseases in the subsequent crop
P < 0.05	-1.6	-3	2	...the cover crop cultivation causes minimal costs
P < 0.0001	-1.24	-2	4	...the cover crop has a high crop rotation compatibility
P < 0.005	-0.36	-1	6	...the cover crop causes few problems with volunteer plants
P < 0.001	0.16	0	8	...the cover crop meets legal requirements
P < 0.0001	0	0	12	...the cover crop looks neat and well-maintained
P < 0.0005	0.26	0	13	...the cover crop returns nutrients to the soil
P < 0.0005	-0.52	-0.1	14	...the cover crop suppresses weeds
P < 0.05	0.36	1	16	...the cover crop helps prevent groundwater contamination
P < 0.0001	1.24	2	20	...the cover crop facilitates field trafficability in spring

Table 5: Distinguishment statements at $p < 0.05$ across three factors.

4.2 Farmers' Viewpoints

In this chapter, the three viewpoints are presented narratively. For some statements, the number and ranking are provided in the format (19: +3), where statement 19 (cover crop can be used as fodder) is rated as very important (+3). Asterisks are used to highlight statements that were ranked significantly differently from other factor groups, with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Table 6 gives an overview about the characteristics of the three factors. It also shows the total number of cover crops that are used specifying the proportion of green manure and fodder crops.

Background Information of Factor Groups

	F1 (n=12)	F2 (n=8)	F3 (n=2)
	Average (min/max)		
Age	41 (31/58)	44 (30/54)	30.5 (29/32)
Farm Size (ha)	41 (0.9/85)	28 (17/45)	71 (58/84)
LSU	36 (0/125)	38 (21/55)	237.5 (75/400)
	Total number		
Cover Corps	34	14	4
Out of it Green Manures	28	3	2
Out of it Fodder Crops	6	11	2

Table 6: Background information of factor groups

4.2.1 Viewpoint 1: “The Regenerative Farmer”

The *regenerative farmer* viewpoint is characterized by 12 farmers, with an eigenvalue of 8.14 and accounting for 30% of the study variance. The average age of participants in this group is 41 years. They manage an average of 36 LSU (median = 24) and operate farms with a mean size of 41 hectares (Table 6). This group comprises five organic farmers, six conventional farmers, and one farmer in transition. On average, these farmers incorporate five crops in their crop rotations. Among the farmers in this group, a total of 34 different cover crops are utilized, with each farmer incorporating at least two varieties. Notably, only one farmer relies exclusively on monocultures, such as phacelia or lupine, while the rest use at least one cover crop mixture. Of the 34 cover crops, 28 are classified as green manures, with just 6 primarily intended for

fodder production (Table 6). This highlights a strong preference for green manure crops, with limited use of those typically suited for fodder.

This identified viewpoint was named *regenerative farmer*, placing high importance on soil health in cover crop practice. Although the term *sustainable farmer* might also be applicable, the emphasis here is specifically on soil health rather than broader environmental objectives such as promoting biodiversity (10: 0), climate change mitigation (17: 0), or preventing groundwater contamination (16: -1). Consequently, *regenerative farmer* more accurately characterizes this perspective.

Most farmers aligned with this viewpoint are part of the regenerative agricultural community or follow its practices. For example, participant P9 believes that healthy soil is fundamental to all other aspects of farming:

“(...)soil life, which is also the foundation for regenerative agriculture. There the principle is not how do I best care for my vegetables, but how do I best care for my soil. Because if I have healthy soil, then my plants are automatically healthy and well fertilized. So, you get away from the learnt thinking of only looking at the plants and instead focus holistically, above all on the soil.”

The regenerative community is growing, with some farmers actively participating. The opportunity to learn from a network is very valuable. P9 adds:

“That is why it is cool to work with “Regenerative Schweiz”. It is a network and there are regular online meetings where you can get advice, exchange ideas and take part in training courses. And it is also very valuable that not everyone has to make the same beginner's mistakes.”

Their involvement in this community has likely influenced the development of this viewpoint.

Farmers who align with this viewpoint place a high priority on humus formation (23: +3) and on the return of nutrients to the soil (13: +3). These practices are considered essential components of their cover crop strategy.

P9: *“I think that if you promote the build-up of humus, then you automatically achieve many other points: you have better trafficability, the soil breathes better, you have better water storage, you have better air inclusion in the soil, so if you do in the sense, I say humus formation, then you also cover a lot of the others. That is why I mentioned it as the most important. Because humus is everything for the soil. If the proportion of hummus in the soil is right, then you have already done a lot of good.”*

A notable divergence from other factor groups is their view on cover crops as fodder (19: -3)*, which they regard as irrelevant. Some farmers pointed out that their primary focus is on soil enrichment rather than on using cover crops for livestock feed (P9 with 21 LSU):

“The cover crop is never relevant for me as fodder (...) it is returned to the soil to build up humus.”

Others either have sufficient fodder (P17 with 48 LSU) and do not depend on cover crops for this purpose:

“There is no point in using cover crops as feed because we already have more than enough with the 1.5 hectares of grass.”

Or no livestock at all making the use of cover crops as fodder unnecessary (P23 with 0 LSU):

“Yes, that is not relevant for us because we do not have any animals and because I prefer to put it directly into the ground where it is.”

The cost of cover crops (2: -2)* is not a primary concern and rather irrelevant for this group. Most farmers who share this viewpoint stated that they are willing to invest more money to foster long-term, healthy soil conditions.

P3: *“About the costs, I think nothing comes from nothing. Green manures are relatively expensive and if you consider the time needed for tilling and sowing, then it can quickly add up to 1000 francs or even more per hectare. But I do not think it pays off 1:1 the next year that you would have much more yield. It is a longer-term process to build up soil.”*

Two other distinguishing statements for this group are that using cover crops to reduce pests in subsequent crops is considered neutral (1: 0)*, and the compatibility of cover crops with high crop rotation is only slightly important for this group (4: +1)*.

Consistent with the regenerative farming perspective, they place high value on achieving loose soil (21: +2) and reduced erosion (22: +2) through cover crop application.

Summarized, the *regenerative farmer* viewpoint is characterized by a strong focus on soil health and long-term sustainability, prioritizing these over immediate economic gains. They emphasize humus formation, nutrient recycling, and soil preservation, reflecting values closely aligned with those of "Regenerative Schweiz". Several farmers also stated that they are part of "Regenerative Schweiz" and follow its principles.

4.2.2 Viewpoint 2: “The Economic Farmer”

Factor 2 includes 8 farmers, with an eigenvalue of 3.65, accounting for 14% of the explained variance. The average age of farmers in this factor is 44 years. On average, the farms associated with this viewpoint are 28 hectares in size and manage 38 LSU (median = 34) (Table 6). Among these farmers, 2 are certified organic, while 6 practice conventional farming. All farmers within this factor have cattle. Among the 8 farmers a total of 14 different cover crops

are used. Every farmer in this group incorporates cover crops suited for fodder production, while only 3 also cultivate green manure cover crops on their fields (Table 6).

For this viewpoint, the considerations of costs and labor investment in cover crop practices are significantly more important compared to other factor groups.

The distinguishing statements include that cover crops incur minimal costs (2: 0)* and require minimal labor (7: 0)*. This emphasis is stronger for this viewpoint than for factor group 1 (2: -2), (7: -1) or factor group 3 (2: -3), (7: -2). One farmer also notes that he prefers not to invest heavily in cover crops because they do not generate direct financial returns. P7:

“Since I did the master school, I have always looked at effort and costs. And the two actually go hand in hand and I now say that effort means costs. (...) Your labor costs, the machine costs, the seeds cost, and you still have the risk that it will not come. Yes, the probability is about 70-80% that you really get something out of it and in this area of “cover crops” you cannot earn any money, you can only recoup your costs. In other words, you can recoup the costs you have incurred. But you cannot make any money from it.”

That the cover crop can be used as fodder is ranked as very important (19: +3). This also makes economically sense as P1 explains:

“So, I find it very important that I can use it as fodder. Primarily, it is also a bit about the economic aspect.”

This viewpoint emphasizes regenerative practices and soil care slightly less than other factor groups do. Specifically, aspects such as humus formation (23: +1)*, soil loosening (21: 0)*, and erosion prevention (22: -1)* are ranked lower. This reduced emphasis may be attributed to a greater focus on other priorities among these farmers as fodder production. For some farmers, the land conditions are already relatively favorable, reducing the need for cover crop interventions, as indicated by P14:

“It is too flat and with the cultivation we do, we never have erosion.”

Only one farmer explicitly stated that he does not support regenerative agricultural practices, citing them as overly ideological. This perspective is expressed by P28:

“But do you know about this regenerative agriculture... we still have to talk about that. They can preach what they want today, but actually, I am not quite so sure. I have to say that achieving a 1% humus build-up with 90 tons of dry matter per hectare is unrealistic. You would not even get that if you planted 10 consecutive wheat crops per year. Someone needs to explain to me how that is supposed to work. It seems like someone just preached it and thought it was cool. But, sorry, no! Not even close. When I see how these weirdos practice, I have to say, they seem to be a group of people who believe it is effective because they have heard it somewhere or move in those circles. But I just have to say, guys, unfortunately, no.”

Farmers in this group generally prioritize statements that have direct effects on subsequent crops over other objectives. They place high importance on returning nutrients to the soil (13: +3), maintaining soil moisture (18: +2)*, suppressing weeds (14: +2), minimizing issues with volunteer plants (6: +2), increasing yields of subsequent crops (9: +1), and ensuring high crop rotation compatibility (4: +1)*. It is notable that they particularly value the role of cover crops in reducing pests and diseases in subsequent crops (1: +1)* more than the other factor groups do. This suggests that farmers in this factor group place emphasis on how cover crop practice directly affect the yields of subsequent crops.

Environmental considerations that have no direct effect on their crop yields are ranked as less important. For instance, climate change mitigation (17: -3)* as illustrated by P11:

“Contribution to climate change mitigation is not really important to me.”

Farmers in the second viewpoint see fodder production as the primary benefit of cover crops. They prioritize cost and labor efficiency over long-term soil health. Unlike *regenerative farmers*, who emphasize humus formation and sustainable soil care, these farmers focus on immediate gains such as nutrient return and pest reduction for subsequent crops. Environmental concerns, such as climate change mitigation, are considered less important.

4.2.3 Viewpoint 3: “The Sustainable-conventional Farmer”

Factor 3 is associated with only two farmers. Additionally, P6 showed a significant negative loading on this factor, indicating that this farmer holds a viewpoint opposite to the one described by the factor. Both farmers linked to this factor are male and younger than those in the other factor groups, with P30 being 29 years old and P12 being 32 years old. Neither farmer is certified organic. One manages 84 hectares of land, while the other manages 58 hectares, both of which are larger than the average land holdings in the other factor groups. Additionally, their LSU values are higher compared to other groups, with P30 managing 400 LSU and P12 managing 75 LSU (Table 6). Both individuals hold diplomas, either a Matura or a master instructor qualification. In total, they use 4 different cover crops: UFA Alpha, UFA Lepha, UFA Regina Gold, and UFA Wintergreen. Whereby UFA Regina Gold and UFA Wintergreen are well-suited for fodder production (Table 6).

The most important consideration for these farmers is that cover crops can be used as forage (19: +3). Additionally, humus formation is also highly valued by both farmers (23: +3). As P30 explains:

„Building up humus, I think that is by far the most important thing, because that has to be the

long-term goal for the soil. I mean, I am 29 now and I have got 30 years ahead. The goal should be for every field to accumulate more humus over those 30 years, not to lose it."

A distinctive feature of this factor group is their high ranking of cover crops' ability to facilitate field trafficability in spring compared to other factor groups (20: +2)*. This preference is closely linked to their choice of cover crops, which are used for a variety of purposes, including fodder production. They employ mixtures such as UFA Wintergreen (ray grass) and UFA Regina Gold (lucerne), which also both help in drawing out water. P30:

"And the grass for our farm is definitely the best. In spring, if you had grass as a pre-crop you will always be able to drive into that field. If you have the field empty or with a green manure, then the soil is much wetter. The grass draws the water out and then you can drive in."

and P12:

"In the cover crop 'Regina Gold' that we had, the plants drew water from the soil after the rain, which made the soil more stable."

The effectiveness of cover crops in reducing pests and diseases in subsequent crops (1: -2)*, their high crop rotation compatibility (4: -2)*, and their ability to suppress weeds (14: -1)* are significantly lower ranked compared to other factor groups. Therefore, these factors are distinguishing statements for this viewpoint. They place greater value on other goals, although they acknowledge that these considerations are not entirely insignificant. As P30 notes:

"For me, the weighting here is less important in relation to other things."

Additionally, since both farmers adhere to conventional practices, they are less reliant on natural solutions such as cover crops to address these issues.

Although they adhere to conventional practices, this does not imply a lack of concern for environmental issues. They regard climate change mitigation (17: +1), biodiversity (10: +1), and groundwater contamination (16: +1)* as relatively important goals, ranking these factors higher than they do in factor groups 1 and 2.

The *sustainable-conventional farmer* viewpoint consists of two younger, non-organic certified farmers who place significant importance on the fact that cover crops can be used for fodder production and humus formation. They emphasize soil stability to improve field trafficability in the spring, while assigning less importance to the role of cover crops in reducing pests, diseases, and weeds. Despite their conventional practices, they place value on environmental goals such as climate change mitigation, biodiversity, and preventing groundwater contamination, ranking these concerns higher than other factor groups.

4.3 Climate Change

For the analysis of the research question II (“How do Swiss farmers perceive climate change, and what measures are they taking to adapt?”) eight categories were identified: Indicators, Negative Consequences, Positive Consequences, Adaptation Measures, Cover Crops, Emotional Response, Climate Change Mitigation, and Miscellaneous. A total of 280 text segments were identified as relevant to this research question (Table 7). Some statements were categorized in more than one category.

Category	Statements	Farmer *
Indicators	50	25
Negative Consequences	68	27
Positive Consequences	14	11
Adaptation	69	26
Cover Crops	23	16
Emotions	15	14
Mitigation	15	9
Miscellaneous	26	15
Total	280	30

*Indicates the number of farmers who made at least one statement in the specified category

Table 7: Overview of text segments and the number of farmers who provided statements in each of the eight categories.

4.3.1 Climate Change Indicators

Farmers in Switzerland have noted various indicators of climate change, with 50 text segments highlighting these observations made by 25 participants. In some cases, a single statement included multiple indicators, as shown by P17:

"But I think the heavy rainfall and long dry periods are already impacts, and we have to get used to that."

As a result, although only 50 text segments were categorized under this theme, more than 50 individual indicators were mentioned. If the same farmer referred to an indicator multiple times, it was only counted once. The numbers in parentheses indicate how many individual farmers mentioned each indicator based on their experiences on their farms.

The most frequently mentioned indicators include: Changed precipitation patterns (12), prolonged dry periods (11), extreme heat (7), higher temperatures (7), extreme weather events (6), and absence of cold in winter (5).

Additionally, 8 farmers referred to changes in livestock behavior or crops. For example, P30 stated:

"I apply the first dose of fertilizer almost a month earlier now because the vegetation period simply starts earlier. That is how I feel it."

Climate change is becoming increasingly noticeable, particularly in the earlier start and longer duration of the growing season, which some farmers report. Moreover, pests are now present year-round, with new species emerging. Another indicator is the changing behavior of cows, which prefer to stay indoors on hot days and are experiencing health issues more frequently.

One farmer noted that weather predictions have become less reliable, while three others recalled having had more snow during their childhoods. Other observed changes include late frosts, year-round tick presence, altered wind patterns, and greater temperature fluctuations. An interesting finding is that 14 farmers specifically used the word "extreme" to describe climate change indicators.

4.3.2 Negative Consequences of Climate Change

The negative consequences of climate change on agriculture are significant, with 68 text segments highlighting these challenges. A total of 27 farmers commented on the adverse effects, making it the category with the highest number of contributors.

One key issue is heat stress affecting livestock, forcing them to spend more time indoors. This leads to higher feed costs not only because they cannot graze as much, but also because high temperatures make it difficult to grow sufficient fodder. Some farmers are concerned that, in the future, financial pressures might force them to consider slaughtering animals as a last resort. One farmer, P11, shared that the particularly hot summer in 2023 resulted in major financial losses, with cows producing less milk and losing weight:

"Last summer, when it was so hot in August, the cows really suffered. I did not have any ventilation back then and they were giving 3-4 liters less milk per day and you could see that they had also become lighter. They had all lost quite a bit of weight, 30-40 kg per animal in those few weeks. If you add that up, then that is 2 tons of meat per 50 cows... and if you then add 10 francs/kilo slaughter weight, then that is 20'000 francs that we have lost."

Farmers frequently reported that climate change is having a wide range of negative impacts on crops, especially due to increased pest activity and more difficult growing conditions. Pest populations have surged, requiring more pesticide use and causing significant crop damage. Crops like potatoes, sugar beets, and corn are becoming increasingly difficult to cultivate due to heightened pest pressure, hotter temperatures, and drier conditions. Sugar beets have shown a decline in sugar content, and potatoes are suffering from reduced yields due to heat stress. Five farmers specifically noted that potatoes are particularly vulnerable and suffering due to climate change, expressing concerns that they may need to abandon potato farming in the future. As P6 explained:

"What adjustments can you really make? Either it still works, or potato farming in this region is over. That is how I see it."

In addition, soil management has become more complicated, with issues such as nutrient lockout and poor soil structure resulting from extreme weather events. Late frosts have caused further damage, especially to fruit trees, as some farmers reported, with frozen blossoms leading to reduced yields.

4.3.3 Positive Consequences of Climate Change

Despite the many challenges, some positive aspects of climate change were reported, though these were mentioned in only 14 statements by 11 farmers.

One benefit is the extended growing season, which allows for more harvests, such as additional grass cuts. Farmers have also been able to grow new crops, like soybeans, in regions of Switzerland where this was previously not possible. Two farmers even mentioned: P10: *"Across all crops, we have fewer problems in a dry year than in a wet year."* and P7: *"I say it is actually better for agriculture and for the plants."*

Additionally, a farmer (P30) with a biogas plant noted increased demand for green energy due to heightened climate change awareness, which has been advantageous for his operations: *"If the issue were not so significant, people would never consider turning off the gas and switching to our green heating."*

Overall, farmers observe or anticipate far more negative than positive consequences of climate change for their farms.

4.3.4 Adaptation Measures

Main Adaptation Measures	Implemented	Farmer	Considered	Farmer
Crop Production				
Adjusting Planting Dates	2	P12, P26	4	P1, P5, P6, P7
Changing Crop Variety	5	P1, P7, P18, P27, P30	1	P7
Cover Crop/ Under Sowing	5	P13, P14, P19, P20, P23	1	P17
Crop Diversification	1	P15	0	
Giving up Culture	1	P13	1	P21
New Crop Type	2	P16, P 24	7	P1, P5, P7, P8, P12, P25, P29
Protected Cultivation	0		1	P21
Water and Soil Resources				
Irrigation	4	P18, P23, P28, P29	1	P16
Rainwater Harvesting	1	P21	0	
Soil Conservation	2	P14, P22	0	
Water Conservation	3	P14, P17, P29	0	
Livestock				
Fodder Adjustment	3	P13, P18, P27	0	
Life-style Adjustment	2	P20, P27	0	
Rearing Livestock	2	P1, P27	0	
Technology				
Ventilation	4	P11, P13, P16, P26	0	
Misting	2	P14, P16	0	
Drying System	1	P4	0	
Crop Management				
Agroforestry	1	P14	2	P2, P5
Insurance	1	P25	0	
Other Measures				
Off-field	1	P22	0	
Total Statements*	43		18	

*Some farmers made multiple unconnected statements about one adaptation measure but are represented only once in this table.

Table 8: Farmers' adaptation measures categorized into five key areas addressing climate change challenges.

Farmers are employing a wide range of climate change adaptation measures to address the challenges posed by climate change, with 43 strategies already in use at the time of the interviews. In total, 20 distinct measures were identified and categorized into five key areas: crop production, water and soil resources, livestock/technology, crop management, and other measures (Table 8).

In the area of crop production, farmers are primarily focused on adjusting planting strategies and selecting crop varieties that are more resilient to heat and drought. For example, five farmers have shifted to well-known drought-resistant crops, such as alfalfa (Luzerne), which thrives thanks to its deep root system. Another key adaptation involves adjusting planting dates, a measure already implemented by two farmers. Additionally, five farmers specifically mentioned the use of cover crops or under sowing practices as part of their climate change adaptation efforts, while another farmer (P17) is considering under sowing but lacks the necessary equipment to implement it at this stage. The introduction of new crop types is the most frequently considered adaptation measure, although many farmers are waiting for suitable varieties that are still under development. One farmer (P16) has already started growing a new potato variety that requires less water, while another (P24) has ordered a newly developed variety to test in the upcoming season. Although crop diversification is currently practiced by only one farmer, it plays a crucial role in reducing the risk of crop failure by spreading it across multiple species. However, the growing challenges posed by climate change have forced some farmers to abandon certain crops. For instance, one farmer (P13) stopped cultivating corn due to repeated extreme weather events in spring:

"We no longer grow corn because we now regularly experience extreme weather events in spring."

Others have discontinued potato farming because of increasing climate risks. Although these cases were discussed in interviews, they were not formally categorized as adaptation strategies and therefore not shown in Table 8, as they did not meet specific classification criteria.

As droughts and high temperatures become more common, protecting water and soil resources is increasingly critical to maintaining agricultural productivity. Five farmers have adopted soil and water conservation techniques, including reduced tillage, enhancing soil organic matter with humus, and planting cover crops to preserve moisture and prevent erosion. Irrigation has also become a crucial adaptation tool, with three farmers currently using irrigation systems. One farmer, P18, is in the process of installing an irrigation system with assistance from the local community, while another is considering it, though the setup may pose some challenges. Since not all farmers have access to sufficient water, alternative solutions are

necessary. For instance, P21 has installed a rainwater collection system in an old building to increase their water supply.

Adapting livestock management practices has become crucial in minimizing the impacts of heat stress on animals, particularly dairy cows. Heat stress, which significantly affects both cow welfare and productivity, is being addressed through various strategies. Three farmers have adjusted their feeding practices to help reduce heat stress. One farmer (P27) highlighted the importance of modifying fodder to reduce heat buildup in the cows' rumen, noting that low-structure fodder with less starch helps keep cows comfortable during hot weather. In addition to changes in feed, some farmers have implemented technological solutions such as ventilation systems (used by four farmers) and misting systems (adopted by two farmers, with another considering it). These technologies are essential for regulating indoor temperatures and ensuring animal comfort during extreme heat. In response to rising temperatures, some farmers are also exploring heat-tolerant livestock breeds, such as the "Australian Primitive Cow", which are better adapted to cope with heat. Furthermore, several farmers provide shaded areas or keep their cows indoors during the hottest hours of the day to further alleviate heat stress. To address fodder shortages exacerbated by climate change, farmers are planting additional grass fields, using cover crops as fodder, and relocating livestock to higher altitudes during summer months to benefit from cooler temperatures. These combined efforts are crucial for maintaining animal welfare and sustaining livestock productivity in the face of increasingly challenging climatic conditions.

Agroforestry, a practice that integrates trees and shrubs into agricultural systems, has been adopted by one farmer (P14), with two others considering its implementation. This approach not only improves local microclimates but also enhances farm biodiversity, contributing to long-term sustainability. In addition, one farmer (P25) emphasized the importance of maintaining insurance, despite its high cost, as a safeguard against climate change. He perceives the risk of losing his entire crop to extreme weather events as significant, having already suffered major losses in 2009 and 2021 due to such events.

On the farm of P22, climate change adaptation measures have primarily focused on off-field actions. One such measure includes constructing a dam to protect their buildings from potential flooding.

4.3.5 Cover Crops

More than half of the farmers do not consider cover crops to be a key measure for climate change mitigation, but they recognize their importance for climate change adaptation. As noted in [Chapter 4.3.4](#), only five farmers specifically identified cover crops as part of their climate change adaptation strategies. Nevertheless, many farmers emphasized the benefits of cover crops in the context of climate change. This category also encompasses broader comments about the connection between cover crops and climate change.

Several farmers emphasized the crucial role of cover crops in adaptation by preventing erosion, retaining soil moisture, regulating soil temperature, and supporting soil organisms. One farmer (P14) noted improved soil and crop resilience with cover crops compared to a neighbor who did not use them:

"You could feel the difference. And his corn was stressed by the drought. Its leaves began to curl, but that was not the case with ours. It is simply because the water retention in the soil is better. That is the only difference we could have had. I think this will be a major issue in the future, managing summer droughts a bit better."

Some farmers are either considering or already implementing under-sowing to establish cover early in the growing season. Some practicing regenerative agriculture view cover crops as a means to enhance humus buildup and sequester CO₂, whereby hemp is noted as particularly effective for carbon sequestration.

4.3.6 Emotional Responses to Climate Change

Farmers report that climate change has a more direct impact on their livelihoods than it has on other professions, due to its immediate effects on agricultural production. For many, the increasing frequency of extreme weather events, such as heavy rainfall and intense heat, leads to frustration and a feeling of helplessness. As two farmers, P5 and P26 explain:

"Yes, these extreme weather events are really stressful. You cannot do anything about it. You are simply at the mercy of it."

And:

"It really makes you think. It causes a certain, how should I say it... not quite helplessness, but it is definitely worrying."

The unpredictability of weather patterns makes farmers feel vulnerable, as they often lack the tools to mitigate the damage to their crops.

Despite these challenges, there is a general sense of resilience among the farming community. Most farmers do not experience overwhelming fear or anxiety in response to climate change.

Instead, they focus on adaptability and flexibility, understanding that change is inevitable. As one farmer, P10, highlights the need to adjust to evolving conditions:

"No, it does not make me anxious. You just have to move with time."

Some farmers also emphasized the importance of finding practical solutions through improved agricultural practices and scientific advancements, P12:

"I am not afraid because I believe there are other ways, and research is working on it."

This demonstrates an underlying optimism in the potential for science and innovation to mitigate the effects of climate change. Nevertheless, some farmers expressed concern about the long-term impacts, especially for future generations and other parts of the world.

Importantly, none of the farmers denied the existence of climate change. They all acknowledged its reality and its growing impact on agriculture, showing that the debate for them is not about whether climate change exists, but rather how to best adapt and respond to its challenges.

4.3.7 Climate Change Mitigation

Farmers frequently bring up climate change mitigation measures, even though this topic was not explicitly addressed in the interviews. These measures include reducing fertilizer use, choosing crops that sequester more CO₂, and increasing soil carbon storage through humus buildup. Biogas plants are also seen as valuable tools for reducing CO₂ emissions. Many farmers emphasize the need for practical and realistic solutions to make agriculture more climate-friendly, and express frustration with external criticisms and unrealistic expectations.

However, most farmers do not view climate change mitigation as the primary goal of their farm operations. Other priorities often take precedence. As one farmer, P17, explains:

"When it comes to climate change mitigation, sure it is important, but on our farm, it is not the top priority. There are other things that matter more."

While climate change mitigation is acknowledged, it is mentioned in fewer statements compared to climate change adaptation (compare Table 7).

4.3.8 Miscellaneous Points about Climate Change

Farmers discussed a variety of topics related to climate change, often extending beyond the primary focus of the interviews.

A recurring theme was the environmental footprint of human activities, with some farmers highlighting the inconsistency of focusing heavily on livestock emissions while overlooking other things. As one farmer (P7) noted:

"We humans have a negative footprint, but it is always livestock and meat production that are blamed for CO₂ emissions."

Farmers also expressed their frustration with the disproportionate emphasis on agriculture in climate discussions while other sectors, such as air travel, face less scrutiny. One farmer commented:

"The younger generation flies so much, and yet we are always being asked about climate measures."

Others criticized consumerism, stressing the need to reduce unnecessary consumption, such as buying excess clothing. These statements reflect a broader view on the importance of personal responsibility in addressing climate change.

The challenge of labor in modern agriculture was another key issue raised. One farmer explained:

"In the past, over 50% of people worked in agriculture, whereas today it is only 4-5%. As a result, chemicals and machinery are necessary, because there are no longer enough workers to do manual labor."

This is highlighting the challenges of maintaining sustainable practices with fewer workers.

Many farmers felt unfairly blamed for CO₂e emissions, emphasizing the role of agriculture in sequestering carbon in soils and the necessity of livestock farming due to Switzerland's topography. One farmer highlighted that veganism cannot easily be adopted on a large scale in Switzerland. Another (P28) expressed frustration with the disproportionate attention given to veganism, stating:

"And the curse is that if somehow 0.5% of the population demands a purely vegan diet, it feels like 10 or 15% or even 25% of people are asking for it. But if you look at it statistically, it is 0.5% who eat vegan and about 4% who are vegetarians. So that is 4.5 people out of 100 who do not consume animal products. But you would think it is 80% of the population with all the noise being made about it, and it really annoys me. If you want to do it, then do it, but stay quiet about it."

However, not all farmers share this view. One farmer (P27) agreed that reducing meat consumption is necessary, saying:

"Reducing meat consumption is the right thing to do."

It just requires a lot of adaptability from the farmers' side:

"If people say we do not need milk, then we will stop milking. Then you might try to use the hills with other animals."

Overall, these discussions reveal the complexity of farmers' perspectives on climate change, balancing personal responsibility, agricultural practices, and societal expectations.

4.3.9 Summary

In summary, the participants recognize that climate change is occurring. They have reported various indicators, and many have already experienced either positive or negative consequences of climate change on their farms. Despite facing numerous challenges, they are actively exploring various adaptation and mitigation strategies to manage these changes, maintaining a proactive rather than fearful or pessimistic outlook on the future.

5 Discussion

5.1 Discussion of the Viewpoints

The primary finding of this study reveals that farmers view cover crops as valuable primarily for either enhancing soil health or for fodder production, as reflected in the responses from the three factor groups: Group 1 (19: -3)*, group 2 (19: +3), and group 3 (19: +3). Soil health or that the cover crop can be used as fodder were consistently ranked as more important than other ecosystem benefits or financial considerations. Singer et al. ([2007](#)) found that over 50% of farmers would plant cover crops if cost-sharing were available. In our study, however, the interviewed farmers were already using cover crops and did not find financial factors to be highly important (2: -2; 0; -3). Still, social desirability might have influenced these responses, causing farmers to downplay the significance of financial considerations ([Grimm, 2010](#)).

Previous research underscores the potential of financial incentives to boost cover crop adoption. For example, Chami et al. ([2023](#)) showed that financial incentives could increase participation in cover cropping by 50%. However, this study did not focus on financial incentives, given that Swiss direct payment programs for cover crops were only introduced in 2023 ([Agridea, 2024](#)). The participants had already been using cover crops before these incentives were available, suggesting their motivations might differ from future adopters. Further research could examine the impact of these financial incentives as the program becomes more established.

Despite meeting the requirements, some farmers in the study noted that they choose not to participate in the new direct payment programs due to perceived administrative burdens or disagreements with the program's conditions. For instance, P7 expressed frustration with the requirement to keep soil bare for no more than seven weeks, suggesting that such regulations do not reflect practical realities:

“But then to make such nonsensical requirements like [maximally leaving the soil bare for] seven weeks. It feels like they just did not consider practical realities in those moments.”

Others have increased their cover crop usage to benefit from the direct payment program. For instance, one farmer (P15) who previously left some fields fallow during short breaks in cultivation now plants fast-growing species like UFA-Express, encouraged by the new financial incentives.

The study identified three distinct viewpoints in cover crop practices using by-person factor analysis.

5.1.1 Regenerative Farmer

While the findings from Q-Methodology reflect farmers' viewpoints, these viewpoints do not always directly translate into behavior. However, some farmers reported that their actions align with their views. Farmers in this group ranked improving soil health as the most important consideration in cover crop practice. In terms of action, some expressed that they not only recognize the importance of soil health but have also actively adopted cover cropping with the specific goal of enhancing soil quality. Additionally, several farmers of this factor group mentioned practicing regenerative agriculture and participating in the "Regenerative Schweiz" network, where cover cropping plays a vital role. During interviews, many participants highlighted the importance of "Regenerative Schweiz" in their transition to regenerative farming. This aligns with findings that identify "Regenerative Schweiz" as a key facilitator in helping farmers adopt regenerative practices ([Stampfli, 2022](#)). Peer-to-peer learning, farmer networks, and knowledge exchange play an important role in facilitating the transition to regenerative farming ([Gosnell et al., 2019](#)).

Cover cropping is widely recognized as an essential tool for improving soil health in regenerative agriculture, with year-round soil cover being one of the five core principles ([Jordan et al., 2022](#); [Khangura et al., 2023](#)). Most farmers who follow regenerative principles actively use cover crops ([Bütikofer et al., 2023](#); [Newton et al., 2020](#)). In the context of regenerative agriculture, using diverse cover crop species rather than monocultures is a common practice ([Khangura et al., 2023](#)). Only one farmer from factor group 1 exclusively used monocultures. All other farmers opted for species mixtures, typically comprising 5 to 12 different species. Some farmers employed mixtures on certain fields, while using monocultures like phacelia or hemp on others.

Farmers in this factor group mentioned that they like to experiment with soil improvement using practices such as effective microorganisms, biochar, and diverse cover cropping. This attitude is similar to that of farmers who share *the innovative steward* viewpoint ([Braitto et al., 2019](#)). In both viewpoints, soil health takes priority over economic considerations, which are regarded as less important ([Braitto et al., 2019](#)). However, while *innovative stewards* place a stronger emphasis on nature-related aspects, *regenerative farmers* in this study rank these aspects slightly lower than the *sustainable conventional farmers*, though they do not disregard them either.

5.1.2 Economic Farmer

Factor group 2 was characterized as *economic farmers*, as they placed greater emphasis on financial factors compared to the other groups. Numerous studies have examined the incentives and barriers associated with adopting cover crop practices ([Singer et al., 2007](#); [Chami et al., 2023](#); [Myers & Wilson, 2023](#)). In a focus group of farmers, it was highlighted negatively that the input costs of cover crops exceed the economic returns ([Roesch-McNally et al., 2017](#)). This perspective aligns with the views of some farmers in factor group 2, who argued that costs are a major concern since cover crops do not provide direct economic profits. For instance, P7 explained that cover crops offer no opportunity for profit. At best, farmers might recover their costs, highlighting the lack of direct financial benefits from this practice.

Generally, the attitudes of farmers classified in this economic group align with the typology of the *productivist*, whose primary objective is food production in a profit-oriented way ([Bartkowski et al., 2022](#); [Burton & Wilson, 2006](#)). This is reflected in this study, as most farmers in factor group 2 place significant value on using cover crops for forage (19: +3) rather than for other purposes.

However, many farmers in this group also engage in activities beyond traditional food production. For example, P28 offers event hosting, and P14 operates a daycare center on the farm. Such diversification deviates from the traditional *productivist* role and is more consistent with a *post-productivist* farming identity ([Burton & Wilson, 2006](#)). The fact that costs (2: 0)* and labor (7: 0)* inputs are not considered trivial is consistent with a *productivist* attitude, where farm profitability is a crucial focus ([Cullen et al., 2020](#); [Beacham et al., 2023](#); [Bartkowski et al., 2022](#)). Numerous studies indicate that climate change is not a primary concern for *productivist farmers*, which might be supported by the ranking of climate change mitigation (17: -3)* ([Hyland et al., 2015](#); [Bartkowski et al., 2022](#)). While farmers in this factor group view climate change mitigation in relation to cover crops as relatively unimportant, this does not necessarily imply that they do not regard climate change as a concern in general. Qualitative interview analysis revealed that all farmers in this group are aware of climate change and are implementing adaptation measures.

5.1.3 Sustainable-Conventional Farmer

The interpretation of factor group 3 is more complex compared to the other factor groups, necessitating a detailed discussion: factor group 3, like factor group 2, utilizes cover crops for fodder production. However, this group also addresses a broader array of environmental goals. In contrast to factor group 1, which primarily concentrates on soil health, factor group 3 incorporates additional environmental considerations. A comparable Q-Sort study on soil management among Swiss farmers identified three factor groups: the *sustainable farmer*, the *pragmatic farmer*, and the *market-oriented traditionalist* ([Bütikofer et al., 2023](#)). In that study, both environmental and soil sustainability were encompassed under the term *sustainable farmer*. In this study, however, a distinction was made between general environmental sustainability and soil sustainability. The *sustainable-conventional farmer* attitude identified as factor group 3 in this study shares some similarities with the *lifestyle farmers* who express environmentally friendly intentions, as described by Karali et al. ([2013](#)). However, a notable difference is that the *lifestyle farmers* in their study had the smallest farm sizes compared to other farmer types, whereas this is not the case in our study ([Karali et al., 2013](#)). In fact, factor group 3 has the largest average farm size at 71 hectares in contrast to factor group 1 with 41 hectares and factor group 2 with 44 hectares.

Two aspects of factor group 3 warrant further discussion, as they appear unusual for this group:

First, the relatively high importance placed on the aesthetic quality of cover crops—"cover crops look neat and well-maintained" (12: 0)*—is notably greater for factor group 3 compared to other groups. Interestingly, Burton and Wilson ([2006](#)) observed that field aesthetics are typically valued by those with a *conservationist* mindset. However, aside from this aspect in particular, factor group 3 does not exhibit many of the other characteristics commonly associated with *conservationist* attitudes. This is further highlighted by the fact that *conservationist* tendencies are usually found among older farmers, whereas factor group 3 has a relatively young average age of 30.5 ([Burton & Wilson, 2006](#)). While it is worth mentioning, no conclusions should be drawn from these demographic characteristics, as the group consists of only two individuals.

Organic farmers typically operate smaller farms compared to conventional farmers ([Sullivan et al., 1996](#)). This finding aligns with our results, as farmers in factor group 3, who practice conventional farming, manage significantly larger farms than those in other factor groups. Additionally, organic farmers generally exhibit higher environmental awareness than conventional farmers ([Läpple, 2012](#)). Despite not being certified organic, the farmers in factor

group 3 demonstrate a positive and environmentally conscious attitude, raising the question of why they have not adopted organic standards.

5.1.4 Across Viewpoints

Although three distinct factor groups were identified, it is important to note that some individuals may exhibit characteristics of multiple factor groups. For example, two farmers in factor group 2 (P7 and P14) reported adopting certain regenerative farming practices, such as reduced tillage and no plowing. However, their underlying motivations appear to be primarily economic. Economic motivations take precedence, with soil health being viewed primarily as a mean to ensure future productivity and profitability ([Beachman et al., 2023](#)). As P7 expressed:

"I do care about the fact that this soil should remain cultivable for a hundred years, (...) I find it important, I think it is great, but there needs to be something in return."

Conversely, factor groups 1 and 3 prioritize personal ideals such as soil health and environmental concerns over economic considerations, which aligns with the *idealist farmer* attitude ([Schmitzberger et al., 2005](#)).

An important insight was that many farmers had not yet considered certain aspects of cover crop practices. For example, some were unaware that cover crops could benefit climate change mitigation or help prevent groundwater contamination. In fact, many encountered these topics for the first time during the sorting process. This highlights gaps in awareness, showing that farmers may not be fully informed about the environmental benefits that cover crops could offer.

It is important to note that farmers were required to rank statements on a grid, which constrained their responses. While they could distinguish between statements of varying importance, many indicated that even those rated as neutral or negative were not considered unimportant. If they had not been restricted by the grid format, most farmers would likely have ranked more statements as important. One farmer found the Q-Sort task particularly challenging, struggling to categorize statements as unimportant given the high significance of all items to him. This suggests that the differences between factor groups may be less pronounced in practice than they appear in this study. Feedback from farmers supports this, with many noting that:

"The statements in the middle were difficult to rank due to minimal differences."

and:

"There were too many statements I found important, so I had to classify some as 'rather unimportant' because they were only slightly less important compared to others, but still significant to me."

5.1.5 Choice of Cover Crops

There were notable differences in cover crop preferences among the farmers in the different factor groups (as shown in Table 6). For instance, all farmers who aligned with the *regenerative* viewpoint used at least one green manure, with only a few also incorporating fodder crops. In contrast, the *economic farmers* showed the opposite trend, with all farmers using fodder crops and only 3 also applying green manures. In the *sustainable-conventional* group, one farmer used three different green manures and fodder crops, while the other relied solely on wintergreen, a crop valued for both animal feed and its ability to promote humus formation.

When these findings are considered alongside the specific priorities of each group in the Q rankings, it suggests that what farmers consider important may actually be reflected in their practices. *Regenerative farmers*, who prioritize soil health, often use green manures that are specifically composed to benefit the soil. *Economic farmers*, who rank that cover crops can be used as forage as very important, consistently apply at least one cover crop suited for that purpose. This suggests that the viewpoints revealed in the Q-Sort analysis may align with their actual farming practices. While the Q-Sort captures farmers' viewpoints, the cover crops they do use provide practical evidence of those priorities being put into action.

The cover crops most frequently used in the study were UFA Lepha, wintergreen, and phacelia (compare [Appendix B](#)). According to Agroscope, the most commonly used cover crops in Switzerland are phacelia and mustard ([Agroscope, n.d.](#)). However, only one interviewed farmer reported using mustard. This discrepancy might be attributed to a recent trend towards using cover crop mixtures rather than monocultures ([Florence & McGuire, 2020](#)). In fact, about two-thirds of the cover crops utilized in this study were mixtures. Among the mixtures, UFA Lepha was the most popular choice.

Cover crop mixtures offer multiple ecosystem benefits ([Chapagain et al., 2020](#)), though they can be more complex to manage than monocultures ([Bybee-Finley et al., 2021](#)). Despite the general belief among some farmers that a diverse species approach yields better results, a review by Florence & McGuire ([2020](#)) found that monocultures and mixtures performed comparably in 88% of cases, with monocultures outperforming in 10% and mixtures in 2%. This stands in contrast with what some farmers in this study stated.

P3: "(...) *Many different plants are important as well. A diverse cover crop is crucial for ensuring root growth in various soil layers. Different plant species also mobilize different nutrients and support microorganisms, which contributes to optimal soil health (...) I recommend sowing at least ten different species.*"

One farmer raised concerns about the lack of information on the relationship between cover crops and soil types. Generally, the existing research focuses more on the overall effects of cover crops on soil rather than on which soil types benefit most from specific species ([Blanco-Canqui et al., 2011](#); [Koudahe et al., 2022](#); [Weerasekara et al., 2017](#)). There are only a few studies that address the interaction between soil types and cover crop practices ([Storr et al., 2019](#)), indicating a need for further research in this area. Another issue may be that while such information exists in academic literature, it may not be accessible to farmers, and advisors or seed suppliers might not emphasize it sufficiently.

Generally, a lot of studies exist that look at different cover crop species and their ecosystem benefits and how they perform compared to each other. But there is still a research gap when it comes to farmers decisions in which cover crop they use and why. More research is necessary to evaluate farmers preferences in cover crop practice and choice of crop species.

5.2 Discussion of Climate Change Perception and Adaptation

While the study provides some numerical insights, these should be viewed as indicative trends rather than definitive statistics due to the limited sample size. Nevertheless, certain topics emerged frequently in discussions with farmers, suggesting their potential significance. However, final conclusions cannot be drawn.

In this study, similar to previous research (e.g., [Kuehne, 2014](#)) all of the farmers acknowledged the existence of climate change. However, some questioned whether it is solely human activities that are responsible, often pointing to natural variability and the unpredictable nature of the climate as additional factors. According to Landwehr et al. ([2023](#)), farmers tend to show more skepticism about climate change compared to other demographic groups. While the present study focused solely on farmers and did not include other demographic groups for comparison, it still does not fully support that claim, as the farmers did not show significant climate skepticism.

Farmers noted that they observed climate change mainly through shifts in precipitation patterns, extended dry spells, extreme heat, rising temperatures, and an increase in extreme weather events. These observations align with findings from previous research ([Pömmer, 2023](#); [Burger-Scheidlin, 2014](#); [Ricart et al., 2023](#)). Roughly a quarter of farmers used the word "extreme" to describe weather changes over the years ([Burger-Scheidlin, 2014](#)). In the present study, 14 out of 30 farmers used the term "extreme" when discussing indicators of climate change.

When comparing the implementation of climate change adaptation strategies by farmers, both similarities and differences emerge when contrasted with the review by Ricart et al. (2022), which identified 16 key adaptation measures. In this study, certain strategies were emphasized to varying degrees. For instance, many participants highlighted cover crops as a key adaptation strategy, whereas they were only briefly mentioned in the review (Ricart et al., 2022). This difference may have been influenced by the prior focus on cover crops during the interviews. Additionally, technological solutions such as ventilation systems, highlighted by participants, were absent from the review. In that review, technology was not classified among the 16 key measures (Ricart et al., 2022). This suggests a possible divergence in adaptation strategies, which may be shaped by geographic or socio-economic factors. The review included studies from a wide array of regions worldwide, which could account for the difference (Ricart et al., 2022). Another notable observation relates to the adoption of "New Crop Type" strategies. While 67% of the farmers in the review implemented this measure, only one farmer in this study had done so, though many others expressed intentions to adopt it in the near future (Ricart et al., 2022). Furthermore, none of the participants mentioned income diversification to reduce dependency on farming. This contrasts with its prominence as a key strategy in the review (Ricart et al., 2022). Possible explanations for this difference might be that Swiss agriculture is less severely threatened by climate change compared to other countries included in the review. Additionally, Swiss farmers are supported by direct payments, which reduce the threat to their income and may encourage them to prioritize practical adaptations over shifting to other sectors. Some farmers mentioned working outside farming, but for reasons unrelated to climate change.

Multiple behavioral factors influence adaptation behavior (Kropf & Mitter, 2022). Although this study did not aim to explore specific links between adaptation behavior and underlying behavioral factors, some brief comparisons were made. Different viewpoints on cover crop practices were identified among the farmers, allowing for comparison. Farmers with a *productivist* attitude tend to seek opportunities in climate change adaptation (Kropf & Mitter, 2022). Group 2, the *economic farmers*, showed similarities to this *productivist* type (see Chapter 5.1.2). However, the 11 farmers who mentioned positive aspects of climate change were not limited to the *economic farmer* group. Farmers from all identified viewpoints recognized potential benefits from climate change.

The interviewed farmers primarily view cover crops as a tool for climate change adaptation rather than for climate change mitigation. This is reflected in the overall neutral to slightly negative ranking of the Q-Statement for climate change mitigation, which had a rank of -0.67. While this score indicates neither strong rejection nor agreement, it suggests that climate

change mitigation is not seen as the primary motivation behind the use of cover crops. However, during the interviews, cover crops were frequently discussed in relation to climate change adaptation. This perspective aligns with various studies that emphasize the role of cover crops in climate change adaptation ([Delgado et al., 2021](#); [Gutknecht et al., 2022](#); [Smit et al., 2019](#)). It is known that when synergies exist, adaptation measures are more likely to be adopted, and cover crops do provide numerous synergies ([Roesch-McNally et al., 2018](#); [Kropf & Mitter, 2022](#)). Nevertheless, some farmers also identified carbon sequestration and reduced fertilizer use as key benefits of cover crops which can be considered indirect contributions to climate change mitigation ([Kaye & Quemada, 2017](#)).

Overall, the interviews revealed a stronger focus on adaptation rather than mitigation measures, a trend also noted in a related study. This study suggests that farmers tend to prioritize adaptation measures over climate change mitigation efforts, likely because adaptation is often seen as a private endeavor, whereas mitigation is considered more of a public responsibility ([Kropf & Mitter, 2022](#)).

Despite acknowledging the reality and challenges of climate change, farmers in the present study exhibit resilience and confidence in their ability to adapt. Unlike other studies that report psychosocial stress, these farmers do not express significant fear or anxiety ([Wittmann et al., 2024](#)). Instead, they focus on practical solutions and trust in scientific advancements to mitigate the effects of climate change. While the unpredictability of extreme weather events causes some frustration and reflection, the general sentiment is one of adaptability rather than helplessness.

To conclude, farmers did not express strong negative feelings about climate change, as they are adapting and are confident in their ability to continue adapting in the future. Although no major adaptation shifts have occurred yet, farmers are gradually adjusting to the changing climate. On the other hand, there is significant potential to motivate farmers to engage more in climate change mitigation efforts. Agriculture has many opportunities to contribute to climate action. With the right support, farmers could play a key role in reducing the sector's environmental impact. However, it is important to acknowledge that farmers face numerous challenges, with climate change being just one among many.

5.3 Further Challenges in Swiss Agriculture

This subchapter addresses additional challenges raised by Swiss farmers during interviews. Though not part of the primary research focus, these issues emerged as significant concerns. Notably, climate change is not the foremost issue for Swiss farmers. Instead, farmers highlighted further challenges, particularly regarding society, trade, regulations, and their operational conditions.

A key concern is the growing disconnection between society and agriculture. Farmers fear that the divide between urban and rural communities is widening, which threatens the future of agriculture. Several studies confirm this view, attributing negative public perceptions of farming to the increasing distance between consumers and agricultural production ([Meyer et al., 2012](#); [Zander et al., 2013](#)). Farmers argue that reintegrating agriculture into society is necessary to foster a better understanding and appreciation of the industry ([von Veltheim et al., 2019](#)).

Another critical issue is the role of the trade sector in sustainability. While consumers are often expected to drive sustainable practices, farmers contend that the trade sector bears significant responsibility. As one farmer, P5, explained:

“The consumer cannot be blamed. If there are three bad apples and one good one, they will take the good one. But that is logical. That is human nature. But the trade sector, that is the problem.”

Many farmers also criticize the profit-driven nature of trade, which prioritizes higher margins and imports over local produce. P9 shared an example:

“And I know farmers who still had 20 boxes of sweet potatoes in storage. But the big retailers took them from Spain because the margins were better there.”

This competition, coupled with low food prices, puts Swiss farmers at a disadvantage, often leaving them reliant on government direct payments to survive ([Rösti, 1997](#)).

However, these direct payments, along with frequently changing regulations, limit farmers' autonomy and ability to plan long-term. P27 voiced this frustration:

“The steering is, in my view, short-term thinking; the programs change every 3-4 years, and that is simply not farming.”

Proposed solutions to these challenges include improving public awareness of agriculture through educational programs, campaigns, and farm visits. Although only one farmer in this study suggested open days as a solution, it is considered a good measure, as other studies emphasize its importance ([Berkes & Mergenthaler, 2020](#)). Many farmers believe that reconnecting the public with agriculture could improve perceptions of the industry ([Zander et al., 2013](#)). Some farmers also suggested a shift toward fairer product prices to reduce reliance on direct payments as a solution. P11 stated:

“But I would prefer a fair and reasonable price for the product. If that was possible, then I would abandon the direct payments.”

In conclusion, the main challenges facing Swiss agriculture are linked to societal expectations, trade practices, and regulatory constraints. Although it was not primarily addressed in this study and broader economic or trade issues were not further explored, understanding farmers' viewpoints remains essential. Further research is recommended to address these concerns and develop more sustainable solutions for Swiss agriculture's future.

6 Research Outcomes, Study Limitations, and Outlook

6.1 Answers to Research Questions

I) What considerations are most important for Swiss farmers in cover crop practices?

To answer research question I, Q-Methodology and analysis with KADE was applied. Three different viewpoints could be identified:

The *regenerative farmers* prioritize long-term soil health through cover crop practice. The most important factor in cover crop practice are humus formation, soil loosening, and nutrient recycling. Their primary goal is to maintain healthy soil over decades, with a focus on the sustainability of soil conditions rather than immediate economic returns.

For the *economic farmer*, the primary goal of cover crop use is fodder production. It is crucial for them to evaluate not only the benefits of cover crops but also the associated costs, including seeds and labor. They are concerned with ensuring that cover crops do not adversely affect subsequent crops and place value on achieving increased yields and short-term profitability through their cover crop practices.

The farmers with a *sustainable-conventional* viewpoint are less concerned about the risks associated with cover crops, possibly as they retain the option to use conventional practices if necessary. Their objectives differ from those of the other two groups, focusing more on the environmental benefits of cover crop practices rather than solely on soil improvement or their direct economic advantages. They place greater value on the positive environmental impacts supported by cover crops compared to the *regenerative farmers* and *economic farmers*. A difference emerged between farmers based on their primary use of cover crops. *Regenerative farmers* primarily use cover crops as green manure, while *economic farmers* predominantly utilize fodder crops. In contrast, *sustainable-conventional farmers* might select cover crops that serve both, environmental benefits and practical needs.

II) How do Swiss farmers perceive climate change, and what measures are they taking to adapt?

To address research question II, qualitative content analysis and inductive categorization were conducted. Swiss farmers exhibit a range of perceptions regarding climate change, though all recognize its presence and effects. Many report the experience of extreme and prolonged weather patterns, increased heat and dryness, and more frequent severe weather events, such as heavy rainfall. These changes have led to negative consequences, including heat stress on livestock, increased pest activity, reduced crop yields, and soil degradation.

Despite these challenges, some farmers see potential opportunities, such as extended growing seasons and the possibility of cultivating new crops like soy. To adapt, they are implementing various strategies, including installing barn ventilation, adjusting grazing schedules, adopting drought-resistant crop varieties, and improving soil moisture retention and temperature stability through reduced tillage and cover crops. Additionally, some farmers address climate change mitigation practices, such as increasing humus levels and optimizing fertilizer use. While farmers are generally proactive and optimistic about adapting to climate change, with hopes for future technological advancements, most are not excessively worried about their own farms. Instead, some express concerns about the broader, global impacts of climate change.

6.2 Study Limitations

As with any methodology, both Q-Methodology and the qualitative content analysis employed in this study have certain limitations, which are briefly outlined here.

Despite careful efforts to include all relevant statements—validated by experts and reviewed during farmer interviews—it is possible that some important aspects of cover crop practices were unintentionally omitted from the Q-Set. For instance, one participant, P4, noted the absence of statements related to the timing of sowing and terminating cover crops.

Additionally, the requirement for farmers to follow a normal distribution when ranking statements posed another limitation. Many farmers stated that this constraint forced them to rank important statements lower than they would have preferred, potentially distorting the results and leading to an inaccurate representation of their true priorities and concerns.

Misunderstandings about the cards and the ranking process also posed challenges. Some farmers may have misinterpreted the statements on the cards, leading to inaccurate rankings. Due to time constraints, it was not possible to discuss each ranking in detail to ensure no misunderstandings occurred.

Moreover, there is a risk that participants provided responses they believed were expected or socially desirable, rather than their genuine opinions. The presence of the researcher during the interviews might have influenced the farmers' responses, introducing bias into the data ([Grimm, 2010](#)).

Another limitation of this study is the potential for reduced reliability and objectivity in the inductive category building process. Since this method does not follow a theoretical framework, it largely depends on the researcher's subjective judgment, which can lead to bias. To address this, researchers often use intercoder reliability, which involves multiple evaluators independently analyzing the same content. Afterward, an index is calculated to measure the

degree of agreement between their results, ensuring a more robust and objective analysis ([Mayring, 2015](#)). Unfortunately, due to time constraints in this study, this step was not implemented, potentially compromising the reliability of the categorization process.

The spatial selection of participants posed another limitation. All interviews were conducted near Bern due to the necessity of using public transport to reach the farms. This geographic constraint may have introduced a regional bias, limiting the representativeness of the findings for the broader Swiss agricultural context. Future studies should aim to include a more geographically diverse sample to better capture the varied experiences and viewpoints of farmers across Switzerland.

6.3 Outlook

6.3.1 Policy Implications

To effectively promote sustainable farming practices, policies must account for the diverse needs and values of farmers, rather than adopting a one-size-fits-all approach. Policymakers should tailor their strategies to specific farming communities, understanding the unique values and motivations of different farmer subgroups in order to create meaningful impact ([Walder & Kantelhardt, 2018](#)).

One of the most effective ways to encourage sustainable practices like cover cropping is through farmer networks. For example, the “Regenerative Schweiz” platform has successfully fostered knowledge exchange among farmers, with many participants in this study reporting valuable insights gained from their involvement in the network. These peer-learning networks can play a crucial role in helping farmers who may lack direct access to resources or expertise. By connecting them with experienced peers, networks can lower initial barriers to adopting cover crops and facilitate their successful integration into farming systems. Expanding the promotion of cover crops through diverse networks, even in communities where soil health is not the primary focus, could further drive adoption. This is because cover crops offer a wide range of benefits beyond just improving soil health, such as climate resilience, water management, and biodiversity enhancement. The study found that farmers aligned with the regenerative farmer perspective are often part of the “Regenerative Schweiz” network, where cover cropping is widely promoted. Therefore, policies targeting this group should focus on further enhancing their knowledge and expertise in cover crop practices, rather than offering incentives for adoption, as these farmers are already likely to implement such practices. Instead, providing advanced training and resources on improving cover crop efficiency might have a more meaningful impact.

For farmers who find economic factors important sharing similar attitude as the *economic farmers*, financial incentives could be a powerful motivator for adopting cover crops. The new direct payment program (implemented in 2023) might lead to increased cover crop up take in Switzerland ([Agridea, 2024](#)). Although this topic was not explored in the present study, it would be valuable to investigate the effect in future research.

A significant opportunity for promoting cover crop adoption lies in raising awareness of the broader ecosystem benefits they offer. In interviews, several farmers mentioned that they had never considered environmental benefits in connection with cover cropping such as climate or groundwater protection. By highlighting positive benefits for the environment targeted outreach efforts could inspire cover crop uptake. Especially eco-conscious farmers who share a similar viewpoint with *sustainable-conventional farmers* might be encouraged to adopt cover crops as a result.

To expand the use of cover crops in Switzerland, particularly in the context of climate change, is becoming increasingly important ([Klein et al., 2014](#)). The content analysis revealed that while some farmers are already utilizing cover crops as an adaptation strategy, there is potential to further promote them as a tool for climate change mitigation. Generally, farmers are actively taking various adaptation measures and express optimism about their ability to cope with climate challenges.

However, efforts specifically aimed at climate change mitigation remain limited. One reason is that farmers face numerous competing priorities, with climate change being just one of many concerns. Policymakers could consider reducing the burden of other regulatory or administrative tasks to make it easier for farmers to focus on climate-related practices. Additionally, it would be valuable to explore and develop further targeted strategies to enhance climate change mitigation within the agricultural sector, ensuring that these efforts are both practical and impactful.

To effectively promote cover cropping and other sustainable farming practices, policies must be customized to address the diverse motivations of farmers. Peer-learning networks, enhanced communication of ecosystem benefits, and well-designed financial incentives are key strategies that can help drive widespread adoption. By understanding and addressing the specific needs of different farmer groups, policymakers can foster meaningful, long-lasting changes that benefit both farmers and the environment.

6.3.2 Further Research

Since this study only briefly examined species preferences, it would be beneficial to further analyze which cover crop species are favored and the reasoning behind these choices, especially in relation to specific environmental and agronomic conditions.

Additionally, studies should investigate the optimal cover crop species for different soil types, as this area is poorly researched. Farmers in this study expressed interest in this topic, noting that there might be significant potential to improve crop performance by tailoring species to specific soil conditions.

Future research should explore the impact of the newly implemented direct payment program that incentivizes cover crop adoption. Understanding how this financial incentive influences farmers' decisions and behaviors would offer valuable insights into policy effectiveness.

Future studies should place greater emphasis on addressing topics that concern farmers most. Even in the context of cover cropping or climate change, it is essential to explore other issues that preoccupy farmers. Many farmers in this study expressed interest in discussing broader agricultural challenges beyond the primary research focus. Since various aspects of farming are interconnected, integrating these broader concerns into research would provide a more comprehensive understanding and contribute to practical, sustainable solutions for the agricultural sector.

7 Conclusion

This study aimed to explore the viewpoints of Swiss farmers on cover crop practices, along with their perception of and adaptation to climate change. Through a mixed-methods approach, including Q-Methodology and qualitative interviews, the research identified distinct viewpoints among farmers, each with different goals and motivations regarding the use of cover crops. The findings provide a nuanced understanding of how different farmer profiles approach cover crop practice. The diversity and complexity of the agricultural sector are evident in the varying viewpoints on cover crop practices, perceptions of climate change, and the different climate change adaptation measures being implemented.

The study revealed three primary viewpoints: *Regenerative farmers*, *economic farmers*, and *sustainable-conventional farmers*. *Regenerative farmers* prioritize soil health and long-term sustainability, emphasizing humus formation and nutrient recycling. *Economic farmers* prioritize fodder production while taking into account financial considerations. Additionally, they place importance on how the cover crop effects the subsequent crop. *Sustainable-conventional farmers* balance environmental goals with practical considerations, using cover crops for both fodder production and soil improvement. These viewpoints underscore the varied motivations and practices among Swiss farmers.

This diversity suggests that one-size-fits-all policies may not be effective, and tailored approaches are necessary to address the specific needs and goals of different farmer groups.

The findings have significant implications for policymakers, extension services, and agricultural advisors. Policies promoting cover crop adoption should consider the diverse motivations of farmers and offer flexible incentives that align with their specific goals. Financial incentives, such as subsidies or tax breaks, could encourage adoption among *economic farmers*, while training and support networks might help *regenerative farmers*. Extension services and agricultural advisors play a crucial role in bridging the gap between research and practice. Providing farmers with practical, region-specific guidelines and facilitating knowledge exchange through workshops could enhance the uptake of sustainable cover crop practices. Additionally, fostering peer networks can help to promote best practices.

Farmers universally acknowledge the presence and impacts of climate change. While most implement adaptation measures, they do not express significant concerns about the climate's effects on their farms and remain optimistic about their ability to adjust. Farmers perceive cover crops primarily as a tool for climate change adaptation rather than climate change mitigation. Interviews revealed that farmers are more concerned about other issues such as the direct payment system, regulations, and the disconnection between society and agriculture. To achieve long-term solutions in Swiss agriculture, it is essential to actively involve farmers in addressing these critical issues and integrate their perspectives into agricultural development.

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into Swiss farmers' views on cover crop practice, climate change perception, and the implemented climate change adaptation measures. By highlighting the diversity of motivations and practices, the research underscores the importance of tailored approaches in promoting sustainable agricultural practices. Continued efforts to support farmers through flexible policies, practical guidelines, and ongoing education will be essential in building a resilient agricultural sector capable of adapting to climate change and other future challenges.

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9 Appendix

Appendix A: Hypothetical Q-Sort

Composite Q sort for Factor 1

-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
...the cover crop looks neat and well-maintained	* ...the cover crop cultivation causes minimal costs	...the cover crop facilitates field trafficability	...the cover crop promotes biodiversity	* ▶ ...the cover crop has high crop rotation compatibility	...the cover crop loosens the soil	...the cover crop returns nutrients to the soil
** ◀ ...the cover crop can be used as fodder	...the cover crop is well-suited for late sowing	...the cover crop reduces soil temperature fluctuations	...the cover crop leads to a lower need for inputs (fertilizers,	...the cover crop increases the yields of the subsequent crop	...the cover crop reduces soil erosion	...the cover crop promotes humus formation
	...the cover crop meets legal requirements	...the cover crop helps prevent groundwater contamination	* ...the cover crop reduces pests and diseases in the subsequent crop	...the cover crop causes few problems with volunteer plants	...the cover crop suppresses weeds	
		...the cover crop cultivation requires only minimal labor	...the cover crop helps attract and sustain beneficial	...the cover crop maintains soil moisture		
			...the cover crop contributes to climate protection			

Figure 5: Hypothetical Q-Sort Regenerative Farmer. Generated in KADE.

Composite Q sort for Factor 2

-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
** ◀ ...the cover crop contributes to climate protection	* ◀ ...the cover crop helps attract and sustain beneficial	** ◀ ...the cover crop reduces soil erosion	** ◀ ...the cover crop loosens the soil	...the cover crop increases the yields of the subsequent crop	* ▶ ...the cover crop maintains soil moisture	...the cover crop can be used as fodder
...the cover crop looks neat and well-maintained	...the cover crop is well-suited for late sowing	...the cover crop helps prevent groundwater contamination	** ▶ ...the cover crop cultivation causes minimal costs	** ◀ ...the cover crop promotes humus formation	...the cover crop suppresses weeds	...the cover crop returns nutrients to the soil
	...the cover crop meets legal requirements	...the cover crop promotes biodiversity	* ▶ ...the cover crop cultivation requires only minimal labor	* ▶ ...the cover crop reduces pests and diseases in the subsequent crop	...the cover crop causes few problems with volunteer plants	
		...the cover crop reduces soil temperature fluctuations	...the cover crop facilitates field trafficability	...the cover crop has high crop rotation compatibility		
			...the cover crop leads to a lower need for inputs (fertilizers,			

Figure 6: Hypothetical Q-Sort Economic Farmer. Generated in KADE.

Composite Q sort for Factor 3

-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3
...the cover crop is well-suited for late sowing	...the cover crop cultivation requires only minimal labor	...the cover crop helps attract and sustain beneficial	** ◀ ...the cover crop returns nutrients to the soil	* ▶ ...the cover crop helps prevent groundwater contamination	...the cover crop reduces soil erosion	...the cover crop promotes humus formation
* ◀ ...the cover crop cultivation causes minimal costs	** ◀ ...the cover crop has high crop rotation compatibility	** ◀ ...the cover crop causes few problems with volunteer plants	** ▶ ...the cover crop meets legal requirements	...the cover crop contributes to climate protection	** ▶ ...the cover crop facilitates field trafficability	...the cover crop can be used as fodder
	** ◀ ...the cover crop reduces pests and diseases in the subsequent crop	** ◀ ...the cover crop suppresses weeds	...the cover crop reduces soil temperature fluctuations	...the cover crop maintains soil moisture	...the cover crop loosens the soil	
		...the cover crop leads to a lower need for inputs (fertilizers,	** ▶ ...the cover crop looks neat and well-maintained	...the cover crop promotes biodiversity		
			...the cover crop increases the yields of the subsequent crop			

Figure 7: Hypothetical Q-Sort Sustainable-conventional Farmer. Generated in KADE.

Legend:

- * Indicates that the statement is a distinguishment statement at $p < 0.05$
- ** Indicates that the statement is a distinguishment statement at $p < 0.01$
- ▶ Indicates that the statement is ranked higher than in the other factor groups
- ◀ Indicates that the statement is ranked lower than in the other factor groups

Appendix B: Applied Cover Crops Overview

Cover Crop Species	Farmers applied
UFA Lepha	7
Wintergrün	6
Phacelia	5
Gras 200er UFA	3
UFA Alpha	3
UFA Express	3
Futtererbs	2
Biodiversitätsgemenge	2
GreenCarbon Fix Sativa	2
Hanf	2
UFA Humus	2
Wickroggen	2
Grünschnittroggen	1
Kleegras	1
Lupine	1
Senf	1
UFA Beta	1
UFA Legufit	1
UFA Reginagold	1
UFA Siloball	1
400er	1
Rajgras	1
Terra Fit (Mühle Rytz)	1
100er Mischung	1
Bio Fit	1
Cerafix	1
Chinakohlrübe	1
Dominanzgemenge	1
Erbsen	1
Gras	1
Grünhafer	1
Grünmais	1
Grünroggen	1
Insect Protect	1
OH Acfruit	1
OH Nährgrün	1
Phacelia-Wickmischung	1
Sandhafer	1
SM 330	1
SM 440	1
Steffen Terrafit nitro	1
Terra fit Tree	1
Terra Green Frigo	1
Trias	1
UFA 106	1
Winterfuttererbsen	1
Total Different Mixtures/ Species	45

Table 9: Cover crops used by farmers according to survey

Appendix C: Interview Guide (English and German)

General Introduction

- 1) Thanking the farmers for their participation
- 2) Introducing myself, the study and the principal of the interview
- 3) Asking again if it is okay that the interview is recorded, let participants sign the consent form
- 4) Asking if they have any further questions
- 5) Tell that recording will start now

1st Part of the Interview: Icebreaker and general overview about farm

Topic	Questions
General Overview about the Farm	Could you give me an overview about your farm? How big is it (ha)? Farming type (organic/conventional/..)? Which are the main crops? Do you have animals (and which)? Where do you sell your products?
Information about the Farmer	Who is involved in the decisions on the farm? What is your role on the farm? For how long have you been farming here? Did you change anything when you took over the farm? What education do you have? Are you working full-time on the farm?
Environmental Circumstances	Do you have erosion here? Can you give me context about the environmental circumstances special for your farm? Did things change lately?
Cover Crops	What does your crop rotation look like? What cover crops do you have? Why did you choose these? Can you describe in 1-2 short sentences what you aim to achieve with them?

2nd Part of the Interview: Q-Methodology

Introduction of Q-Sort	Next, I have a small task for you. I brought cards with statements that relate to what is important to you when working with cover crops. It's only about your own farm and what is personally important to you. So, there is no 'right' or 'wrong', but your opinion is what matters, in the context of your specific situation with cover crops.
Get an Overview of Statements	1) Read the cards carefully 2) Decide whether what's written on the card is important, neutral or unimportant for your own situation/farm 3) Make three piles with what is important, neutral and unimportant

- 4) If you have questions don't hesitate to ask
- 5) If you want to comment something please feel free to do so

Rank Statements on Grid

- 1) First take the stack with the unimportant statements.
- 2) Start with putting those on the grid on the very left "least important"
- 3) Take the stack with the most important and make the same.
- 4) Order the more neutral statements in the middle

Let Participants Review Again

Please look again if you think the ranking are according to your preference. If you want to make any additional changes, please do so now.

Document it

Ask if it is final now
Take a picture

3rd Part of the Interview: Reflexion

Most and Least Important

Why did you decide to put those two statements most/least important?

Difficult to Rank

Were there any cards that were hard to order on the grid? Which and why?

Missing Statements

Do you think that there is an important consideration you have in cover crop practice missing? If yes, which?

4th Part of the Interview: Semi-structured Questions to Climate Change

General about Future

If you think in the future what things are relevant on your farm?
Are there things, you plan to change or implement?

Climate Change

- Do you notice climate change on your farm? How do you notice it?
- Do you take adaptation measures? Which ones? (Cover Crops)?
- How do you feel about climate change? Does it worry you?
- What else do you want to say about climate change?

Other Topics

Is there anything else you want to talk about?
You think you could say everything you wanted?

End of the Interview

- 1) Say that if there is nothing they want to add, the interview is over now.
- 2) Thank again for the interview.
- 3) Ask for other potential interview partners.
- 4) Turn of the recording.
- 5) Reaffirm that they can always contact me for questions or concerns regarding the study.
- 6) Ask if I should send the thesis as soon as it is written.
- 7) Give the quick survey to fill in.
- 8) While letting fill in the survey, put all interview material back and make a scan of the consent form.

Generelle Einführung

- 1) Bei den Landwirt: innen für die Teilnahme bedanken.
- 2) Kurze Vorstellung über mich, die Studie und das Ziel sowie Hintergründe der Studie.
- 3) Erneut nachfragen, ob das Interview aufgenommen werden kann. Einwilligung unterzeichnen lassen.
- 4) Nachfragen, ob es noch Unklarheiten oder Fragen gibt.
- 5) Informieren, dass die Aufnahme beginnt.

1. Teil vom Interview: Eisbrecher Fragen, genereller Überblick über Betrieb, Person

Thema	Fragen
Genereller Überblick Betrieb	Könntest du mir einen Überblick über den Betrieb geben? Wie gross ist er (ha)? Welchen Produktionsstandard (bio/ konventionell/..)? Welches sind die Hauptkulturen? Habt ihr Tiere (und welche)? Wohin verkauft ihr die Produkte?
Informationen über Landwirt: in	Wer ist in die betrieblichen Entscheidungen involviert? Was ist deine Rolle auf dem Hof? Seit wann. Praktizierst du auf diesem Hof? Hast du irgendwas verändert bei der Hofübernahme? Welchen Bildungshintergrund hast du? Arbeitest du Vollzeit auf dem Betrieb?
Naturräumliche/ Umwelt Bedingungen	Habt ihr Erosion? Kannst du mir Kontext spezifische Informationen über die Umweltbedingungen geben, die für den Betrieb relevant sind? Hat es sich in der letzten Zeit verändert?
Zwischenfrüchte	Wie sieht deine Fruchtfolge aus? Welche Zwischenkulturen hast du? Warum hast du dich für diese entschieden? Kannst du kurz in 1-2 Sätzen beschreiben, was deine Ziele damit sind?

2. Teil vom Interview: Q-Methode

Einführung von Q-Sort	Als nächstes habe ich eine kleine Aufgabe für dich. Ich habe Karten mit Aussagen mitgebracht, die sich darauf beziehen, was dir in der Zwischenfruchtpraxis wichtig ist. Es geht dabei nur um deinen eigenen Betrieb und was dir persönlich wichtig ist. Es gibt also kein „richtig“ oder „falsch“, sondern es kommt nur auf deine Meinung an.
Überblick über die Aussagen bekommen	1) Lies die Karten genau durch 2) Entscheide, ob diese Aussage für deinen Betrieb und dich wichtig, neutral oder unwichtig ist. 3) Mache drei Stapel mit wichtig, neutral und unwichtig. 4) Wenn du Fragen zu einer Karte hast oder generell zur Aufgabe kannst du mich jederzeit gerne fragen. 5) Wenn du Kommentare zu den Aussagen machen möchtest, darfst du das gerne machen.

- Ordne die Karten auf der Vorlage**
- 1) Nimm als erstes den Stapel mit den unwichtigen Aussagen.
 - 2) Lege die unwichtigsten zwei auf der Vorlage ganz nach links zu der unwichtigsten Spalte. Und so weiter.
 - 3) Nimm den Stapel mit den wichtigen Aussagen und mache das gleiche.
 - 4) Nun kannst du die neutralen Aussagen in der Mitte ordnen.

Nochmals durchsehen lassen, ob die Einordnung so passt. Bitte schau noch einmal ob dieses Abbild so für dich passt.
Falls du noch Änderungen vornehmen möchtest, kannst du das jetzt gerne machen.

Dokumentieren Nochmals nachfragen ob es nun passt.
Ein Foto machen

3. Teil vom Interview: Reflexion

- Wichtigste und unwichtigste** Warum hast du diese zwei Aussagen als wichtigste/unwichtigste eingeordnet?
- Schwierig einzuordnen** Gab es Karten, die schwierig einzuordnen waren? Welche und warum?
- Fehlende Aussagen** Gab es Aussagen, die du vermisst hast? Also gibt es wichtige Sachen für dich in der Zwischenfruchtpraxis, die nicht aufgeführt waren? Welche?

4. Teil vom Interview: Semi-strukturierte Fragen zum Klimawandel

- Generell über die Zukunft** Wenn du in die Zukunft denkst, welche Sachen sind für deinen Betrieb relevant?
Gibt es Sachen, die du verändern oder neu implementieren möchtest?
- Klimawandel**
- Bemerkest du den Klimawandel auf deinem Betrieb? Wie bemerkst du ihn?
 - Nimmst du Anpassungsmassnahmen vor? Welche? (Zwischenfrüchte)?
 - Wie fühlst du dich bezüglich dem Klimawandel? Macht er dir Sorgen?
 - Möchtest du sonst noch etwas zum Klimawandel sagen?
- Andere Themen** Gibt es noch andere Sachen, die du gerne ansprechen möchtest?
Denkst du, du könntest alles sagen, was du sagen wolltest?

Interview Ende

- 1) Wenn es nichts mehr anzufügen gibt, sind wir am Ende vom Interview angekommen.
- 2) Herzlichen Dank für die Teilnahme.
- 3) Hast du Vorschläge für weitere Interviewpartner: innen.
- 4) Aufnahme beenden.
- 5) Versichern, dass sie sich bei Bedenken oder Fragen zur Studie jederzeit an mich wenden können.
- 6) Fragen, ob Interesse an den Ergebnissen der Studie besteht und ich die Masterarbeit zusenden soll.
- 7) Kurzer Fragebogen zum Ausfüllen geben.
- 8) Während der Fragebogen ausgefüllt wird alle Interviewmaterialien zusammenpacken und Einwilligung scannen.

Appendix D: Coding Guideline

Category	Definition	Anchor Example	Coding Rule
Indicators	Indicators are concrete observations or experiences where the impacts of climate change directly or indirectly manifest. These can include changes in weather patterns, seasons, or natural phenomena that occur over extended periods and deviate from usual patterns.	<i>P3: "These hot summers that we've had recently are just more intense, and they happen more often. I can hardly remember when we last had a normal summer. Either it pours rain like crazy, or it is dry for weeks."</i>	A quote will be coded as an indicator of climate change if it clearly describes an observation or change in the weather or environment that the speaker attributes to climate change. This includes extreme weather events, shifts in seasons, unusual temperature or precipitation patterns, and changes in plant growth or animal behavior that were not seen in the past.
Negative Consequences	Negative consequences describe the impacts of climate change that farmers perceive as clearly harmful or problematic. These impacts must be explicitly related to climate change and arise either directly from weather conditions or long-term changes. It must be clear that the consequence is considered negative, either through the content of the statement or its context.	<i>P24: "But the problem is, there are simply new pests. The warmer the climate, the longer warm weather lasts, and then new pests come from the south."</i>	A quote will be coded as a negative consequence if it clearly expresses that a direct impact of climate change is perceived as harmful. This can manifest in the form of crop failures, economic losses, increasing pest pressure, or other negative effects on the farming operation. The description must either explicitly emphasize the problem or clearly indicate that the change has negative consequences.
Positive Consequences	Positive consequences refer to advantages or improvements that farmers experience due to climate change. These must be explicitly described as positive. The impacts must be clearly related to climatic changes and perceived as beneficial by the farmers.	<i>P10: "That we can now plant soybeans and sunflowers. When I started, I wanted to plant sunflowers, but they said that was impossible here, you can forget about it. And it was the same with soybeans. [...] And then we had these dry summers, so I just tried it, and it worked out easily, and now everyone is doing it. Yes, these are the positive impacts."</i>	A quote will be coded as a positive consequence if the farmer explicitly describes that a result of climate change is perceived as an advantage. This can refer to improved growing conditions, new cultivation possibilities, higher yields, or other positive changes. The statement must clearly highlight the positive benefit that the climatic changes bring.
Adaptation Measures	Climate-related adaptation includes actions that are explicitly and consciously taken with the goal of responding to the impacts of climate change. These actions are intended to mitigate the negative effects of climate change. It must be clear that the adaptation specifically targets climate change and is not coincidentally addressing its effects.	<i>P20: "The problem is simply the summer droughts and such, which are becoming more challenging. We have reacted by sending the cows to the mountains. We have fewer animals in the summer. That's the thing. That started in 2019."</i>	A behavior is coded as adaptation if: The measure is explicitly presented or formulated as a reaction to climate change. There is a direct reference to climate changes (e.g., temperature rise, droughts, extreme weather events), and the action is aimed at countering them. The adaptation is consciously made or considered to either prevent the negative effects of climate change or mitigate its impacts. Accidental benefits from an action that do not explicitly target climate change will not be coded as a climate adaptation. Statements that imply an adaptation which has not yet been implemented but is being seriously considered in a concrete way can also be included in this category.

Cover Crops	Includes all statements that mention the word "cover crop" in the context of climate change or clearly indicate that the discussion is about the use of cover crops in relation to climate change.	<i>P29: "The cover crops retain moisture in the soil, that's a statement ... and the soil temperature, that's also correct, it has a function ... and with the increasingly hotter years and hotter temperatures, you have to be careful..."</i>	Statements will be coded when the word "cover crop" is explicitly used or when it is clear that the conversation is about cover crops and their role in climate change. The statements can cover both the benefits and challenges or doubt related to cover crops. Statements about general agricultural practices without a clear link to cover crops or their role in climate change will not be coded.
Climate Change Mitigation	Climate change mitigation includes measures and actions aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions or sequestering carbon dioxide (CO ₂) to slow climate change or mitigate its effects.	<i>P3: "Maybe it's the biochar. That's an important aspect to protect the climate. Because it binds CO2 in the soil for millennia, and on the other hand, it also stimulates humus formation in the soil. Not only the carbon that you put into the soil with biochar, but it also has a trigger effect because microorganisms like biochar, they settle there, and that leads to even more humus formation."</i>	A statement will be coded as climate change mitigation if it explicitly describes actions or measures that aim to reduce CO ₂ emissions or sequester carbon with the clear goal of combating or mitigating the effects of climate change. This can include both technical measures and sustainable agricultural practices. The speaker's intention to contribute positively to climate protection through these actions must be clear. Alternatively, a statement will also be coded if it mentions the word "climate protection/mitigation."
Emotions	Refers to statements that explicitly address the emotional reactions or personal feelings of the farmers in relation to climate change. This category includes both direct feelings such as fear, worry, or relief, as well as indirectly expressed emotional reactions to the challenges and uncertainties brought about by climate change.	<i>P26: "I'm not afraid of anything in life. But yes, it makes you think. It does make you think. It already makes you feel a certain, how do you say it? Maybe not quite helplessness. But it is certainly alarming when you see how quickly things have changed."</i>	Statements will be coded when clear emotions or feelings such as fear, worry, stress, confusion, anger, or relief in relation to climate change and its impacts on farming or personal life are mentioned. Emotions must be explicitly stated or strongly implied (e.g., by referring to stress from extreme weather or uncertainty). Statements that are purely factual or technical without reference to personal feelings will not be coded.
Miscellaneous	Addresses climate change but not directly related to agricultural adaptation strategies or specific climate protection measures. This category includes general opinions, personal beliefs, observations, and discussions about climate change, as well as aspects beyond direct farming impacts, such as consumer behavior, societal developments, or the role of CO ₂ certificates.	<i>P17: "And animal products are increasingly coming under scrutiny. I understand that to some extent, but I also think the consumer doesn't understand the topography of Switzerland. And 70% of the land here is grass, and none of the vegans eat grass, and they don't maintain the Alps. You can't reverse that cycle. Some things are just given."</i>	Statements are coded if they relate to climate change but not specifically to agricultural adaptations or climate protection measures. The statements should be more general in nature and can reflect personal opinions, observations, societal trends, or considerations about consumer behavior. Statements can criticize societal behaviors or reflect on global developments in the context of climate change. Statements that directly discuss agricultural practices for adapting to climate change or specific measures for climate protection (these fall under other categories) will not be coded.

Table 10: Coding Guideline

Appendix E: Survey (English and German)

Interviewdata Place:, Date:, Time:					
Year of Birth:	Gender	<input type="checkbox"/> male	<input type="checkbox"/> female	<input type="checkbox"/> other	<input type="checkbox"/> k.A.
Agricultural education level (highest completed)	<input type="checkbox"/> no agricultural education	<input type="checkbox"/> agricultural school lower secondary; vocational	<input type="checkbox"/> agricultural school higher secondary; vocational master	<input type="checkbox"/> agricultural university degree.	<input type="checkbox"/> k. A.
Farm manager since:	<input type="checkbox"/> < 5 years	<input type="checkbox"/> 5-14 years	<input type="checkbox"/> 15-30 years	<input type="checkbox"/> > 30 years	<input type="checkbox"/> k. A.
Betriebsmerkmale					
Farm Size (in ha) (without forest):		Organic: <input type="checkbox"/> yes <input type="checkbox"/> no <input type="checkbox"/> partly			
Thereof crop land(ha):		Acquisition: <input type="checkbox"/> Main income <input type="checkbox"/> Side income <input type="checkbox"/> KA			
Thereof rented land (ha):					
Farming Type (mainly)	<input type="checkbox"/> Field Crops	<input type="checkbox"/> Horticulture	<input type="checkbox"/> Permanent Culture	<input type="checkbox"/> Grazing Livestock	<input type="checkbox"/> Pigs/Poultry <input type="checkbox"/> Mixed
Livestock (LSU or Number).....					
Number of Crops in Usual Rotation:					
Environmental measures (if yes, which?):					
Cover Crops (which and since when?):					

Interviewdaten: Ort:, Datum:, Zeit:					
Geburtsjahr:	Geschlecht	<input type="checkbox"/> männlich	<input type="checkbox"/> weiblich	<input type="checkbox"/> anderes	<input type="checkbox"/> k.A.
Höchste abgeschlossene landwirtschaftliche Ausbildung	<input type="checkbox"/> keine landw. Ausbildung	<input type="checkbox"/> landw. Schule ohne Matura; Lehre	<input type="checkbox"/> landw. Schule mit Matura; Meister	<input type="checkbox"/> landw. Hochschulabschluss	<input type="checkbox"/> k. A.
Betriebsleiter:in seit:	<input type="checkbox"/> <5 Jahre	<input type="checkbox"/> 5-14 Jahre	<input type="checkbox"/> 15-30 Jahre	<input type="checkbox"/> >30 Jahre	<input type="checkbox"/> k. A.
Betriebsmerkmale					
Betriebsgröße (in ha) (ohne Wald):		Bio: <input type="checkbox"/> Ja <input type="checkbox"/> Nein <input type="checkbox"/> Teilweise			
davon Ackerfläche (ha):		Erwerbsart: <input type="checkbox"/> Haupterwerb <input type="checkbox"/> Nebenerwerb <input type="checkbox"/> KA			
davon gepachtete Fläche (ha):					
Betriebsart (hauptsächlich)	<input type="checkbox"/> Feldfrüchte	<input type="checkbox"/> Gartenbau	<input type="checkbox"/> Dauerkultur	<input type="checkbox"/> Weidevieh	<input type="checkbox"/> Schweine / Geflügel <input type="checkbox"/> Gemischt
Nutzvieh (GVE oder Anzahl):					
Anzahl Kulturen in Ihrer typischen Fruchtfolge:					
Agrarumweltmaßnahmen (wenn ja, welche?):					
Zwischenkultur (welche und seit wann?):					

Table 11: Survey English and German

Appendix F: Consent Form (German)

Es ist uns wichtig, dass alle Teilnehmer:innen an unserem Forschungsprojekt vollständig darüber informiert sind, was ihre Teilnahme an dem Projekt bedeutet und dass sie ihre freiwillige Zustimmung zu ihrer Teilnahme geben.

Wir betrachten den Schutz der Privatsphäre bei der Verarbeitung personenbezogener Daten als ein wichtiges Thema, dem wir in unseren Prozessen grosse Aufmerksamkeit widmen. Die Verarbeitung Ihrer personenbezogenen Daten erfolgt nur mit Ihrer freiwilligen Zustimmung.

Bitte lesen Sie die folgenden Informationen sorgfältig durch und bestätigen Sie Ihr Einverständnis:

- Ich bestätige, dass ich **freiwillig** am Forschungsprojekt teilnehme und dass ich weiß, dass ich jederzeit davon zurücktreten kann (z.B. das Interview abbrechen oder später die Daten löschen lassen).
- Ich bestätige, dass ich ausreichende **Informationen** über das Forschungsprojekt erhalten habe und dass ich die Möglichkeit hatte, Fragen dazu zu stellen die ausreichend beantwortet wurden.
- Ich bestätige, dass das Interview zu Analysezielen **aufgezeichnet** wird und dass die Tonaufnahmen nach der Transkription in pseudonymisierten Text gelöscht werden.
- Ich habe verstanden, wie meine **Daten verwendet werden** (z.B anonymisiert, für Forschungszwecke, Aufnahmen werden im Anschluss gelöscht, Abbruch des Interviews oder Ausstieg aus Forschungsarbeit möglich) und **welche Rechte ich als Betroffener habe**.

Name:

Ort, Datum:

Unterschrift:

Declaration of consent

on the basis of Article 30 of the RSL Phil.-nat. 18

Name/First Name:

Registration Number:

Study program:

Bachelor

Master

Dissertation

Title of the thesis:

Supervisor:

I declare herewith that this thesis is my own work and that I have not used any sources other than those stated. I have indicated the adoption of quotations as well as thoughts taken from other authors as such in the thesis. I am aware that the Senate pursuant to Article 36 paragraph 1 litera r of the University Act of 5 September, 1996 is authorized to revoke the title awarded on the basis of this thesis.

For the purposes of evaluation and verification of compliance with the declaration of originality and the regulations governing plagiarism, I hereby grant the University of Bern the right to process my personal data and to perform the acts of use this requires, in particular, to reproduce the written thesis and to store it permanently in a database, and to use said database, or to make said database available, to enable comparison with future theses submitted by others.

Place/Date

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Tischler', written in a cursive style.

Signature